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Abstract

(300-500 words)

This deliverable documents the work within the MOLAB Transnational Access (TNA) program in the IPERION HS project during the period M28-48. Herein the relevant operations that were carried out in WP4 MOLAB: access to mobile laboratories to provide selected User groups through competitive calls with on-site access to non-invasive portable instrumentation and competences are described. The operations of the userhelpdesk and internal platform helpdesk as a support to users at each step of the MOLAB experience from project application to project completion and fulfilling of post-access duties is documented (T4.1). The assessment of projects chosen by the Peer Review Panel in the fifth and sixth calls are chronicled in detail, along with the objectives and content of all the 16 projects that were provided with access inclusive of previous calls. The organization and efforts of each access provider (including the number of Users and the days of access) are provided with an overview of the main outcomes that were attained (T4.2). Activities of outreach and dissemination carried out by the MOLAB providing teams and Users are outlined (T4.3). Crucial elements of data management could be elaborated through the implemented report for Users (T4.4). Finally, all MOLAB access activities could be monitored according to the quality system and set key performance indicators, where the MOLAB TNA program was successfully completed.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science (this Project)
ERIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
SC	Steering Committee
Mx.	Month N. X after project start
TNA	Transnational Access
M-PRP	MOLAB Peer Review Panel
PM	Person-Months per Participant

Narrative (technical) description

INTRODUCTION

The European Research infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) aims to establish a distributed infrastructure of collaborating facilities of renowned excellence to provide access to advanced scientific instruments, data and specialist knowledge to further the advancement of science and innovations in the field of heritage science. The goal of the TNA program in IPERION HS has been to incorporate the current practices into the next stages of E-RIHS ERIC's imminent deployment and operation.

To accomplish this goal, the TNA program, which is at the center of IPERION HS, has continued to provide a wide range of access services that are focused on meeting the research demands of the European and Associated Countries heritage scientific community. Users have the opportunity to access exclusive European resources for both in-situ and laboratory investigations on artwork materials and sites through access to three physical TNA platforms in IPERION HS—ARCHLAB (WP2), FIXLAB (WP3), and MOLAB (WP4). This combined activity fosters the advancement of cutting-edge research in the examination and conservation of works of art. An automated modality of application for TNA has been tested for the duration of IPERION HS where each platform has been managed by respective Coordinators being connected by a single entry point and respectively integrated in terms of adopted procedures. The continuing objective of these access programs has been to provide eligible Users, whether beginners or experts, with methodological approaches, compliant best practices, tools, and technologies in addition to experimental resources so they can conduct their research projects in settings where they otherwise would not be able to.

The Mobile LABoratory, MOLAB, specifically, composed of 19 distinguished laboratories (<https://www.iperionhs.eu/molab/>) is located throughout ten European and United Kingdom nations for in-situ non-invasive measurements of artworks, collections, monuments, and sites. MOLAB offers access to 38 different high-performance and well-integrated portable experimental techniques (ranging from point analysis, 2D/3D analyses, multi/hyperspectral imaging and mapping and remote sensing). The consolidated MOLAB ethos entails the instrumentation moving to the site where the User is working, be it an archaeological site, museum, restoration workshop, or on scaffolding. Dedicated MOLAB operators assemble the various instrumentation/s *in-situ*; carry out the measurements in direct collaboration with the User and research questions and simultaneously co-foster knowledge on interpretation and discussion of results with the Users. This activity contributes to diffuse a real and effective culture of cooperation between cultural heritage high technologies, scientists, operators, and researchers in the field of humanities, making a significant benefit to mobility, education and networking, linking research and innovation. This deliverable outlines the continued effort and work by the MOLAB platform in this last period of IPERION HS.

1. CONTINUING AND FINALIZING WORK

The main focus and concentration of the final 20 months (M28-48) in IPERION HS has been to fulfil the objectives of the MOLAB program by providing transnational access to Users. Even though access commenced at M18 due to the effects of the worldwide pandemic supplying an unforeseen set of unique challenges and constraints, MOLAB has been steered for a continued coordination and development of activities, based on the set targets of calls for proposals, selections of projects, project organization and executions. Following the re-distribution of budget and number of accesses to be completed by each providing facility, attention was placed on overseeing the remaining calls, project selections in accordance with available facility slots, organizations and executions whilst delivering a quality service to users pre-, during- and post- access.

Herein the progressive activities are reported in depth, that have been planned and carried out. Commencing with assistance to potential MOLAB Users for queries, project optimizations, interaction with providing facilities and any general information relayed to the fully functional MOLAB Helpdesk from the overseeing UserHelpdesk. The combined experience by providers and coordination of the implemented dashboard and its internal functioning for the project feasibility assessment and the closing of successful proposals following access provision is documented. The continued work of the MOLAB peer review panel (M-PRP) in evaluating and ranking the proposals submitted to call 5-6 according to a set of criteria implemented for the TNA program is discussed. The implementation and development of relative access projects from all calls with excerpts of research objectives and preliminary results and efforts of each provider are accounted. The collection and publication of User post access duties with regards to Users' Reports feedback through the User Satisfaction form are all considered. Efforts of dissemination of MOLAB through presentations of activities at conferences, User meetings, webinars oriented to Users, and diffusion through media for the involvement of the public are all then mentioned.

1.1. The UserHelpdesk

The UserHelpdesk, with single entry point Userhelpdesk@iperionhs.eu has consistently provided an integrated User support service for the complete TNA program for the duration of the entire project. The desk has responded to all User queries either directly or by forwarding to the individual platform providers/coordinators for technical information, potential risks and logistics information. The MOLAB Helpdesk, molab.iperionhs@ispc.cnr.it operating in T4.1, has offered support to potential MOLAB Users in the proposal preparation stage with regards to optimal experimental set-ups. At the same time, the helpdesk is aware of the availability of slots with regards to the provider and as to the correct working order of each piece instrumentation. It has also acted as a source of communication for the providers so that they are aware of the outcomes of each of the calls and for primary assistance in the planning of access. The UserHelpdesk directly oversees the dashboard (details below) and is of technical assistance for the User, providers and coordinators alike.

1.2. MOLAB experiences of the automatic dashboard

A representative of each MOLAB facility/laboratory with all their specific techniques offered in IPERION HS has had access to the dashboard system and has assisted the coordination office towards its fuller optimization. Since the opening of the project providers have been directly alerted by automatic e-mails as to activity within their personal dashboard requesting MOLAB instrumentation offers

(see inset). The providers have been able to successfully oversee the feasibility assessment of each individual project proposal submitted at each call and have had the opportunity to flag any query or logistic requirement related to each instrument in any

ID	ACRONYM	SERVICE NAME	USER	TYPE	CREATED	FEASIBILITY	COMMENTS	ACCESS CARRIED OUT	PROPOSAL STATUS	ALERT
mol_1	DIACOMM	Total reflection mid/linear FTIR	patrick.casati@muu.se	New	2021-07-23 08:22:36	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	
mol_22	EPHA	Total reflection mid/linear FTIR	cesar.escobarclaros@oieo-atlantique.fr	New	2021-11-27 15:15:45	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	
mol_24	HFTV-ReVis	High resolution digital microscopy	hbrek@eie.gr	New	2021-11-28 19:14:36	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	
mol_24	HFTV-ReVis	Total reflection mid/linear FTIR	hbrek@eie.gr	New	2021-11-28 19:14:36	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	
mol_34	BellMod	High resolution digital microscopy	eveline.vandepuette@gmail.com	New	2022-02-23 16:08:00	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	
mol_34	BellMod	Total reflection mid/linear FTIR	eveline.vandepuette@gmail.com	New	2022-02-23 16:08:00	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	
mol_34	BellMod	Micro Raman (A exc 532 nm)	eveline.vandepuette@gmail.com	New	2022-02-23 16:08:00	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	
mol_39	MoMNeoSaf	Raman spectroscopy (exc 785 & 1064 nm)	thea.wintherg@nkaarkivet.se	Resubmission	2022-04-28 15:53:53	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	
mol_39	MoMNeoSaf	Total reflection mid/linear FTIR	thea.wintherg@nkaarkivet.se	Resubmission	2022-04-28 15:53:53	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	
mol_47	Synthetic vortices	Total reflection mid/linear FTIR	laura.homer@nasjonalmuseet.no	New	2022-04-29 15:03:50	yes	Edit this comment	yes	CLOSED	

specific proposal. These comments could be communicated to the proposer via the UserHelpdesk who has vision of the entire TNA platforms feasibility along with the corresponding Coordinators with rights to over-ride decisions. The time frame for the technical feasibility was set to 2 weeks following the call deadline and in most cases was respected by providers. It was noted that if a facility changed provider representative, then communications were necessary to insert the new representative. This will likely be refined in the future so that more than one reference person can be nominated per facility and will receive dedicated e-mail alerts. All feasible projects could then be passed to the MOLAB Peer Review Panel (M-PRP) to make their evaluations offline. Again this step was rather labour intensive as all documents regarding each proposal had to be exported and communicated externally. On finalizing the selection at each call, the results of each project were re-inserted into the dashboard with both the User and provider being adequately notified automatically. Following the access campaign, the responsible provider could close the project in the dashboard and provide an indication of the amount of access given therein. The users following this closing of access had a time period of 2 months to provide the post access user duties in their dashboard by attaching the user report and by filling out the user satisfaction survey. **Bottlenecks** were noted in the flow when providers did not close their access so the user was not timely informed to carry out their post access duties. The userHelpdesk often encouraged providers to close their access to mitigate this situation. Beyond such, the dashboard has been essential to a smoother running of TNA for MOLAB and has been of enormous benefit for the monitoring and gathering of all data necessary for quality purposes.

1.3. The MOLAB Peer Review Panel (M-PRP)

The **Peer Review Panel (PRP)** composed of acknowledged experts selected outside the consortium has overseen the scientific evaluation, scoring and ranking of all TNA feasible submissions. A separate PRP has existed for each separate platform. For MOLAB, the PRP has observed the same

four members with continuity: *Dr. Alison Heritage*- Conservation Research Specialist, ICCROM, Italy. *Dr. Marc Walton*- Head, Conservation and Research at M+ Museum for Visual Culture, Hong Kong. *Dr. Elsa Bourguignon*: Head of Research Lab Unit at Louvre Abu Dhabi and *Dr. Arianna Traviglia*- Coordinator of the Centre for Cultural Heritage Technology, IIT, Venice, Italy. Each member is individually recognised for their expertise in applications in fields of non-invasive analyses of cultural heritage. This scientific panel has overseen the evaluation of every proposal based on the integrated IPERION HS weighted peer review criterions (see inset). Following a provisional ranking normally within a month following feasibility assessment, a meeting could be tempestively organized with the platform coordinator for discussion and a final selection of proposals granted access. The communication and availability of the MOLAB PRP is praised for an efficient evaluation following each call.

CALL:		PROPOSAL ACRONYM:			
General Evaluation					
CRITERIA	Points range	Points awarded	Coefficient	Total points	Comments
Scientific Excellence	1 - 5		7	0	
Assessment of the state of the art of the topic and of the advancements of the field	1 - 5		5	0	
Valorisation and dissemination plan	1 - 5		4	0	
Expertise of User Group	1 - 5		3	0	
Potential Impact	1 - 5		1	0	
TOTAL POINTS (out of 100):				0	
Conclusions					
Final Comments:					
Strong points :					
Weak points:					
Recommendations :					
I hereby declare that I have been objective and impartial in my work as Peer Review Panelist. I also declare that I consider the information provided to be confidential and that I will not divulge it without the prior authorisation of the project leaders of the project.					
Name:					
Date :					
Signature:					

1.4. Participated events and publications

Information on transnational access and performances of the MOLAB facilities, has been also diffused through presentations through online/ in-presence international conferences or workshops and through publications within the international scientific literature. A list compiled by T4.3 includes presentations at conferences and workshops (invited lectures and oral or poster communications) typically attended by researchers in the field of Heritage Science are reported where MOLAB has been presented and had a clear visibility:

- Organizers VISPEC 2023 School (12th-16th June, Perugia) “In-situ sessions with portable systems of the MOLAB platform of European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (ERIHS) at the Galleria Nazionale dell'Umbria” (MOLAB.it Laura Cartechini, David Buti, Francesca Rosi);
- Invited VISPEC 2023 Conference (12th-16th June, Perugia) “Vibrational spectroscopy for the study of cultural heritage materials: recent developments in hyperspectral macro imaging” (MOLAB.it Costanza Miliani)
- Invited TECHNART 2023 (Lisbon 7-12 May) “Strengthening the MOLAB platform of E-RIHS through advanced hyperspectral chemical imaging at the macro-scale” (MOLAB.it Francesca Rosi)
- Invited Workshop Spectral imaging for CH (NTNU Gjøvik November 6-8 2023) “Broad range advanced hyperspectral imaging in Heritage Science: the MOLAB experience within the access activity of the E-RIHS infrastructure” (MOLAB.it Francesca Rosi)
- Invited IV Seminario Internazionale di diagnostica Artistica IMAGO ARTIS Le nuove immagini Scientifiche e la Conservazione tra nuove frontiere tecnologiche e sguardo storico-critico (20-21 Aprile 2023, Roma) “Tecnologie avanzate per l’imaging iperspettrale: sviluppi e applicazioni a casi studio attraverso l’attività del MOLAB” MOLAB.it (Francesca Rosi, Laura Cartechini, Aldo Romani, Costanza Miliani)
- Invited MATHCES 2022 1st Workshop on Mathematical Challenges to and from new technologies (22-23 June 2022 Rome La Sapienza University) "Hyperspectral imaging in

- Heritage Science: the MOLAB experience” (MOLAB.it Francesca Rosi, Laura Cartechini, Aldo Romani, Francesco Paolo Romano, Costanza Miliani)
- Invited Workshop RIS (Reflectance Imaging Spectroscopy) Rijksmuseum 28th Septemebr 2022 “RIS in the extended mid-infrared range: past and recent developments, limitations and strengths: Enhancing the capacity of the European Mobile Laboratory MOLAB” (MOLAB.it Francesca Rosi, Costanza Miliani, Laura Cartechini, Aldo Romani, David Buti)
 - Poster 20th ICOM-CC Triennial Conference (Valencia 22-23 September 2023) Model system development for the in-situ monitoring of metal soap protrusions DUIVENVOORDEN Jorien, Donata Magrini, Francesca Rosi, Georgios Karagiannis, Haida Liang, Jana Striova, Katrien Keune, Piotr Targowski (MOLAB.it, MOLAB.uk, MOLAB.pl)
 - Workshop MACH2023 - Mathematical modeling and Analysis of degradation and restoration in Cultural Heritage, Roma (Italy), 11-15/09/2023, “A combined experimental and computational modeling approach to study the color change of painted surfaces” Invited lecture (MOLAB.it Monico L.) (Letizia Monico, Aldo Romani, Costanza Miliani, Koen Janssens)
 - XX Congresso Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica dell'Ambiente e dei Beni Culturali - Società Chimica Italiana, Ischia (Italy), 28th September – 1st October 2023, “Prevent the color changes in paintings: a multi-material, multi-technique and multi-scale approach” Plenary Lecture (MOLAB.it Monico L.)
 - XVI Synchrotron radiation school “Gilberto Vlaic” (SILS), Trieste (Italy), 19-30/09/2022, “Synchrotron radiation-based X-ray techniques & cultural heritage objects: an integrated multimaterial, multi-technique and multi-scale approach to study their composition and evolution” Invited lecture (MOLAB.it Monico L.)
 - 108° Congresso Nazionale della Società Italiana di Fisica, Milano (Italy), 11-16/09/2022, “Synchrotron radiation X-ray methods and non-invasive spectroscopies to preserve the beauty of colors in paintings” Plenary lecture (MOLAB.it Monico L.)
 - 15th International School and Symposium on Synchrotron Radiation in Natural Science, ISSRNS 2022, Cracovia (Poland), 22-25/08/2022, “Multiple scale length studies of cultural heritage materials and objects by synchrotron radiation X-ray methods and non-invasive spectroscopic techniques” Invited lecture (MOLAB.it Monico L.)
 - Gordon Research Conference - Scientific Methods in Cultural Heritage Research, Les Diablerets (Switzerland), 10-15/07/2022 “Predicting and Preventing the Color Change of Painted Surfaces with Experimental and Computational Modelling” Invited lecture (MOLAB.it Monico L.)
 - EXRS 2022, Bruges, 26th June – 1st July 2022, “Properties and stability of cadmium-based paints probed by state-of-the-art analysis at multiple length scales” Oral Presentation (MOLAB.it Monico L.),
 - PhD Academy, Venice International University, Preserving and Safeguarding the Beauty of Cultural Heritage; Fundamentals, Methods and Applications of State-of-the-Art Diagnostic Tools Using Optical, X-Ray and Particle Probes, Venezia (Italy), 6-10th november 2023 (scientific coordinators: Massimo Carpinelli, Letizia Monico, Roberto Senesi, Warren S. Warren; <https://www.univiu.org/study/phd-academy/preserving-and-safeguarding-the-beauty-of-cultural-heritage>; lecture: ERIHS - European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (MOLAB.it Costanza Miliani, CNR))
 - Festival della Scienza 2023, “Impressione di colore. Nuove tecnologie per i beni culturali”, Genova, 24th October – 3rd November 2023(<https://www.scitec.cnr.it/component/content/article/28-eventi/192-23e020?Itemid=163>)

- 6th International congress CHEM-CH, 4th-8th July 2022, Ravenna (Italy) “Shedding Light on the Factors Triggering the Degradation Path of Green Copper and Arsenic-based Paints by a Multi-method Approach at Multiple-scale Lengths” (Sara Carboni Marri, Letizia Monico, Francesca Rosi, Costanza Miliani, Riccardo Vivani, Aldo Romani) Oral presentation (MOLAB.it Sara Carboni Marri),
- XXXVIII Interregional Meeting of the Società Chimica Italiana-Sections of Toscana, Umbria, Marche, and Abruzzo (TUMA2022), 1st-2nd September 2022, Perugia (Italy), “Shedding Light on the Factors Triggering the Degradation Path of Green Copper and Arsenic-based Paints by a Multi-method Approach at Multiple-scale Lengths” (Sara Carboni Marri, Aldo Romani, Francesca Rosi, Riccardo Vivani, Costanza Miliani, Letizia Monico) Oral presentation (MOLAB.it Sara Carboni Marri),
- Historical Materials BAG meeting, 5th-6th December 2022, Grenoble (France) “Shedding Light on the Factors Triggering the Degradation Path of Green Copper and Arsenic-based Paints: a focus on XRD measurements with conventional sources and synchrotron radiation” (Sara Carboni Marri, Aldo Romani, Francesca Rosi, Riccardo Vivani, Costanza Miliani, Letizia Monico) Oral presentation (MOLAB.it Sara Carboni Marri),
- VISPEC conference, 14th-16th June 2023, Perugia (Italy), “Reflection Infrared Spectroscopy: a promising tool to monitor the degradation state of paintings containing emerald green” (Sara Carboni Marri, Aldo Romani, Francesca Rosi, Riccardo Vivani, Costanza Miliani, Victor Gonzales, Geert Van der Snickt, Koen Janssens, Letizia Monico) Oral Presentation (MOLAB.it Sara Carboni Marri),
- XX Congresso Nazionale della Divisione di Chimica dell'Ambiente e dei Beni Culturali (ABC) - Società Chimica Italiana, 28th September-01 October 2023, Ischia (Italy), “New insights into the degradation path of emerald green in oil paintings” (Sara Carboni Marri, Aldo Romani, Francesca Rosi, Riccardo Vivani, Costanza Miliani, Victor Gonzales, Geert Van der Snickt, Koen Janssens, Marine Cotte, Olivier Mathon, Francesco D’Acapito, Letizia Monico) Oral Presentation (MOLAB.it Sara Carboni Marri),
- PhD Academy, Venice International University, Preserving and Safeguarding the Beauty of Cultural Heritage; Fundamentals, Methods and Applications of State-of-the-Art Diagnostic Tools Using Optical, X-Ray and Particle Probes, Venezia (Italy), 6-10th november 2023, “New insights into the degradation path of emerald green in oil paintings” (Sara Carboni Marri, Aldo Romani, Francesca Rosi, Riccardo Vivani, Costanza Miliani, Victor Gonzales, Geert Van der Snickt, Koen Janssens, Marine Cotte, Olivier Mathon, Letizia Monico) Poster (MOLAB.it Sara Carboni Marri)
- CHEMCH2022 - 4th -8th July 2022_“*Complementary multimodal imaging provides insight on Old Man in Warnemünde by E. Munch*” M. Bertasa, R. Fontana, E. Grifoni, A. Impallaria, M. Raffaelli, J. Striova, I.C.A. Sandu, J. Ferrer, Ch. Andraud, A. Tournié, F. Rosi, L. Cartechini, D. Buti, F.P. Romano, C. Caliri, C.G. Fatuzzo, G. Privitera, Z. Preisler, C. Costantino, A. Romani (Oral contribution MOLAB.fr)
- “MOLAB: Bringing science to heritage objects of research”, Conferenza: 6th International Congress "Chemistry for Cultural Heritage" CHEMCH2022, Università di Bologna, Ravenna, 08/07/2022 Invited Speaker (MOLAB.it David Buti),
- Oral contribution (MOLAB.it D. Magrini, A. Andreotti, I. Bonaduce, D. Buti, M. P. Caggia, E. Cantisani, C. Conti, F. D’Andria, T. Ismaelli, E. Possenti, S. Vettori), “Ancient polychromy and surface treatments on clay and limestone sculptures and architectures at Castro (Lecce)”, Conferenza: The Materiality of Polichromy, 11th International Round Table on Polychromy in Ancient Sculpture and Architecture, Musei Capitolini and Museo Nazionale Romano, Roma, 9-12/11/2022

- Oral contribution (MOLAB.it Davide Domenici, David Buti, Costanza Miliani), “Nuovi studi sui mosaici mesoamericani del Museo delle Civiltà”, Convegno internazionale "CONNESSIONI. Oggetti, saperi, parole, culture e civiltà", Museo delle Civiltà, Roma, 16-18/11/2022
- “The Painting materials of Codex cospi”, Conferenza: Coloquio “Códice Cospi: vida, contenidos y significados de un manuscrito mesoamericano”, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Históricas, Città del Messico, 25/01/23 Invited Speaker (MOLAB.it David Buti),
- TECHNART 2023 - International conference on analytical techniques in art and cultural heritage, Lisbona, 7-12/05/2023 Contributo Orale (MOLAB.it D. Buti, C. Caliri, B. Doherty, D. Domenici, G. Privitera, D. Magrini, C. Miliani, L. Paderni, A. Romani, F.P. Romano, F. Sabatini, F. Rosi), “Mesoamerican Mosaics from the collection of Museo delle Civiltà (MUCIV): A Multi-analytical scientific study”
- PolymEr Research Studies for PreventivE Conservation through non invasIVe analytical strategiEs (PRIN2022), Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Roma, 12/01/2024 Contributo orale (MOLAB.it David Buti), “E-RIHS – The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science”, Kick-off Meeting PERSPECTIVES -
- Photonics 4 Cultural Heritage - LE TECNOLOGIE FOTONICHE al servizio del settore dei beni culturali, Milano, Castello Sforzesco, 01/12/2023, “From X-ray to radio wave: the multi-technique diagnostic of the European mobile laboratory MOLAB”, Invited lecture (MOLAB.it A. Romani)
- IX Ciamician Photochemistry School from Fundamentals to Applications, Department of Chemistry "Ciamician" - Alma Mater Studiorum - University of Bologna, 6-9/06/2022 “How much photochemistry can there be in an artwork?” Invited Lesson (MOLAB.it A. Romani),
- La “Tavolozza” Periodica, dove chimica ed arte si incontrano, Liceo Classico e Artistico “Luca Signorelli”, Cortona, 31/10/2023 and Liceo Scientifico “G. Mazzatinti”, Gubbio, 28/02/2024 Invited Lesson (MOLAB.it A. Romani),
- Mostra IL MONDO A COLORI: uno sguardo su arte, pigmenti e minerali, a cura di Sabrina Nazzareni e Aldo Romani, Museo Archeologico Nazionale dell’ Umbria, 28/04 – 31/10 2023
- Oral Communication: Claudia Caliri, Andrea Busacca, Claudia Fatuzzo, Danilo Pavone, Giulia Privitera, Zdenek Preisler, Costanza Miliani, Francesco Paolo Romano. C., A novel MA-XRF scanner operated with a 6-SDDs hodoscopic system for painting investigation, EXRS2022 - European Conference on X-Ray Spectrometry, Bruges, 28 June - 1 July 2022
- -Oral Communication: Francesco Paolo Romano, Costanza Miliani, Claudia Caliri, Claudia Giuseppina Fatuzzo, Danilo Paolo Pavone, Giulia Maria Privitera, Dario Zappala and Zdenek Preisler, A novel MA-XRD/MA-XRF scanner for pigment-specific mapping of paintings, EXRS2022 - European Conference on X-ray Spectrometry, 26 June- 1 July 2022, Bruges, Belgium.
- -Oral Communication: Irina Sandu, Jin Ferrer, Francesca Rosi, David Buti, Letizia Monico, Donata Magrini, Claudio Costantino, Laura Cartechini, Aldo Romani, Costanza Miliani, Francesco P.Romano, Claudia Caliri, Claudia G. Fatusso, Giulia Privitera, Zdenk Preisler, Raffaella Fontana, Anna Impallaria, Emanuela Grifoni, Marco Rafaelli, Jana Striova, Christine Andraud and Aurélie Tournié, Colours of modernism in Edvard Munch's paintings from Warnemünde period, COLOURS 2022, 14-16 September 2022, Évora University, Portugal
- -Oral Communication: Francesco Paolo Romano, Costanza Miliani, Claudia Caliri, Claudia Fatuzzo, Danilo Pavone, Giulia Privitera, Dario Zappalà & Zdenek Preisler, New developments on simultaneous MA-XRD/MA-XRF imaging: instrumental setup and computational approaches for pigment-specific mapping of paintings, 7th IP4AI meeting 2022 -

Computational approaches for technical imaging in cultural heritage, 27-29th April 2022, Virtual Conference.

- -Oral Communication: F. P. Romano, C. Miliani, C. Caliri, C. Fatuzzo, D. Pavone, G. Privitera, D. Zappalà, Z. Preisler, New developments on simultaneous MA-XRD/MA-XRF imaging: instrumental setup and computational approaches for pigment-specific mapping of paintings, CHEMCH2022- 6th International Congress Chemistry for Cultural Heritage, 4 - 8 July 2022 - Ravenna, Italy
- -Oral Communication: Francesco Paolo Romano, Costanza Miliani, Claudia Caliri, Claudia Giuseppina Fatuzzo, Giulia Maria Privitera, Eva Luna Ravan, Dario Zappalà and Zdenek Preisler, A novel MA-XRD/MA-XRF scanner for pigment-specific mapping of paintings, TECHNART2023 International conference on analytical techniques in art and cultural heritage, 07-12 May 2023, Lisbon
- Oral Communication: Claudia Caliri, Claudia Giuseppina Fatuzzo, Danilo Paolo Pavone, Giulia Maria Privitera, Eva Luna Ravan, Zdenek Preisler, Costanza Miliani and Francesco Paolo Romano, A novel mobile MA-XRF scanner based on a hodoscopic multi-detector system for application in the cultural heritage field, TECHNART2023 International conference on analytical techniques in art and cultural heritage, 07-12 May 2023, Lisbon
- Oral Communication: Fauzia Albertin, Aldo Romani, Claudio Costantino, David Buti, Letizia Monico, Francesca Sabatini, Donata Magrini, Claudia Caliri, Claudia G. Fatuzzo, Zdenek Preisler, Francesco Paolo Romano, Costanza Miliani, Aurélie Tournie, Christine Andraud, Irina Crina Anca Sandu, Jin Strand Ferrer, Giorgio Luciano, Laura Cartechini and Francesca Rosi - Multi-source data fusion of modern complex paintings, TECHNART2023 International conference on analytical techniques in art and cultural heritage, 07-12 May 2023, Lisbon
- -Oral Communication: Caliri C., Busacca A., Fatuzzo C.G., Pavone D.P., Ravan E.L., Preisler Z., Miliani C., Ranocchia G., Romano F.P., Discovering a textual layout in the unrolled carbonized papyri from Herculaneum by the new highly sensitive MA-XRF scanner developed at ISPC-CNR, 109° Congresso Nazionale SIF, Salerno, 11-15 settembre 2023
- E.Cano (MOLAB.es) "E-RIHS e IPERION HS: grandes infraestructuras de investigación para la Ciencia del Patrimonio" in III Meeting of PTI-PAIS, "Trayectoria con Entidades Asociadas" Madrid, 9 June 2022
- TechnArt 2023 Conference Presentation: "Revealing unseen evidence of the hand of Masolino, Masaccio and Lippi in the Brancacci Chapel frescoes" A. Dal Fovo, J. Striova, E. Pampaloni, I. Lunghi, M. Raffaelli and R. Fontana. Poster: "Study of an early 20th century artist's forgery of a Botticelli portrait painted in tempera on tile", A. Dal Fovo, J. Striova, S. Innocenti, L. Sepiacci, and R. Fontana *May 7-12, 2023, Lisbon, Portugal*
- Science in Cultural Heritage (Interdisciplinary thinking) at TUM School of Engineering and Design Lehrstuhl für Restaurierung, Kunsttechnologie und Konservierungswissenschaft Invited Lecture: "Optical methods in conservation studies", A. Dal Fovo. *December 22, 2022, Munich, Germany*
- Lacona 13th Conference, Lasers in the Conservation of Artworks Presentation: "Novel integration of non-invasive imaging techniques for the analysis of an egg tempera painting by Pietro Lorenzetti", A. Dal Fovo. *September 12-16, 2022, Florence, Italy*
- VIII th edition of The International Inventions and Innovations Salon TRAIAN VUIA", Timișoara , 8-10 Oct 2022, M. Dinu, MOLAB.ro
- Optoelectronic developments with impact in Heritage Science – MOLAB-ro, M. Dinu, oral presentation at "Optoelectronics for R&R Processes", 29-30 Sep 2022, online

- ETICCH 2023", Sibiu, 26-27.09.2023 *Optoelectronics sustainability in Heritage Science*, at "Emerging Technology and Innovation for the Conservation of Cultural Heritage - M. Dinu, invited lecture (MOLAB.ro)
- Haida Liang, Invited annual lecture for the Royal Academy of Engineering, East Midland branch, October 2022 [examples of remote sensing techniques used in MOLAB shown]
- Haida Liang, Invited annual lecture for Institute of Conservation (ICON), November 2022 (examples of various IPERION HS MOLAB activity shown)
- Florence Liggins et al., <https://spie.org/optical-metrology/presentation/Large-scale-historical-wall-painting-analysis-and-visualisation-using-multimodal/PC12620-24> SPIE Optical Metrology, Optics for Arts, Architecture and Archaeology (O3A) IX, 26-27 June 2023, (Remote spectral imaging and spectroscopy used in Mustair project)
- Florence Liggins et al., "Understanding the Carolingian artist through a novel workflow involving multimodal remote and in-situ spectral imaging and spectroscopic techniques" 30th EAA Annual Meeting in Rome in session #787, "Artists and Craftsmen. Multidisciplinary Approaches in the Analysis of the Production of Early Medieval Wall Paintings", 28-31 August 2024 <https://www.e-a-a.org/EAA2024/> (results of pigment use at Mustair combined the UK, French and Italian MOLAB)
- Haida Liang, plenary talk, METROARCHAO 23rd Congress in Rome, 19 - 21st October 2023 (examples from Vergina project shown)
- Haida Liang, invited talk, CrysInArt workshop, Amsterdam, 1st February 2024 (long distance remote spectral imaging and Raman spectroscopy for built heritage, examples from MOLAB shown)
- Haida Liang, Invited talk, Middle Infrared Coherent Sources 2024 (MICS 2024) Topical Meeting, 2024 High Brightness Congress, 12-14 March 2024 in Vienna, Austria (long wavelength OCT and remote MIR spectral imaging shown)

MOLAB in collaboration with WP7 and WP8 have continued to participate in the HS Academy activities providing a key source of updated information on MOLABs' heritage science facilities and expertise and access program (see online flyers below). The current topics series has seen lectures given by MOLAB providers on the instrumentations and applications they provide within the project: Piotr Targowski "Optical Coherence Tomography for examination of artworks"(MOLAB.pl); Vivi Tornari "Principles of halographic interferometry for non-destructive subsurface examination (MOLAB.gr). The User meetings arranged also with the HA academy series provided details of the User experience directly from the Users themselves in the MOLAB projects- 2nd Call "GRANJA" Historical evolution of high-quality glass pieces from the Spanish Royal Glass Factory; 1st Call "NIBOTRAP" Non-destructive Identification of Bromoil, Oil and Transfer Photographs

LECTURE SERIES

HSAcademy

Current topics

Lecture #01 / October 26th, 2023

OPTICAL COHERENCE TOMOGRAPHY FOR EXAMINATION OF ARTWORKS

PIOTR TARGOWSKI

HSAcademy
Current topics

Lecture 1 (2023-24) : Optical Coherence Tomography for examination of artworks

The 1st lecture of the 2nd edition "Current Topics in Heritage Science" series was delivered by Piotr Targowski live and online, on October 26, at 4 pm (CEST). The speaker introduced OCT technique and instruments. On examples from the practice, he showed how the OCT technique may be used to examine the structure of various artworks, trace former conservation attempts, and help monitor some restoration procedures.

Watch the video

Lecture #02 / October 26th, 2023

PRINCIPLES OF HOLOGRAPHIC INTERFEROMETRY FOR NON-DESTRUCTIVE SUBSURFACE EXAMINATION

VIVI TORNARI

HSAcademy
Current topics

Lecture 2: Principles of holographic interferometry for non-destructive subsurface examination

The Lecture was delivered by **Vivi Tornari**, Senior Specialized Scientist, Head of the Holography Laboratory of Laser Applications at the IESL of the Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas (Crete, Greece). It is focused on the basic principles and prominent applications of Holographic Interferometry non-destructive examination of movable and immovable heritage objects.

Watch the video

HSAcademy

IPERION HS TNA ACCESS

USERS MEETINGS

ONLINE EVENTS

User meeting #05 / Mar 12, 2024

IPERION HS MOLAB

Cristina Ruiz-Recasens

Marta Oriola-Folch

Raquel Freixas-Jambert

User meeting 5: Raquel Freixas-Jambert, Cristina Ruiz-Recasens and Marta Oriola-Folch

The 5th IPERION HS Users meeting was held online on **March 12th, 2024 at 3 pm (CET)** using the ZOOM platform.

Raquel Freixas-Jambert, Cristina Ruiz-Recasens and Marta Oriola-Folch presented their MOLAB project: Non-destructive identification of bromoil, oil and transfer photographs.

Watch the video

User meeting #04 / Feb 13, 2024

IPERION HS MOLAB

Teresa Palomar

HSAcademy

User meeting 4: Teresa Palomar

The 4th IPERION HS Users meeting was held online on **February 13th, 2024 at 3 pm (CET)** using the ZOOM platform.

The User Group Leader **Teresa Palomar** shared her experience related to the TransNational Access (TNA) projects of access to IPERION HS Molab services. She presented her project on the characterization of historical glass GRANJA, with the part of scientific analysis implemented with the support of IPERION HS services.

Watch the video

Press Releases

The MOLAB action by MOLAB.fr and MOLAB.cyi in the 1st Call project "PYRITEDINOSAUR" : OCT, 3D structure -light scanner and integrated XRD-XRF applied to conservation dinosaurs fossils with pyrite decay and evaluation of innovate method conservation, appeared in a series of online newspapers and social outlets (31/05/2023)

<https://www.diariodelaltoaragon.es/noticias/aragon/2023/05/31/la-conservacion-de-los-fosiles-de-arino-protagoniza-una-investigacion-multidisciplinar-de-varias-instituciones-165574-daa.html>

La Fundación Dinópolis, la Escuela Superior de Conservación y Restauración de Bienes Culturales de Aragón y el Instituto de Nanociencia y materiales de Aragón están llevando a cabo una investigación sobre los mecanismos de alteración de los sulfatos que contienen los fósiles de Ariño.

La Fundación Conjunto Paleontológico de Teruel - Dinópolis (FCPTD), La Escuela Superior de Conservación y Restauración de Bienes Culturales de Aragón y el Instituto de Nanociencia y materiales de Aragón están llevando a cabo una investigación sobre los mecanismos de alteración de los sulfatos que contienen los fósiles. Dicha estudio forma parte del proyecto denominado PYRITEDINOSAUR, dentro del programa I4U2S (Molab Laboratorio) que se encuentra dentro de la plataforma IPERION HS (Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science), está financiado con fondos europeos y cuenta con una infraestructura de equipos móviles acompañados por técnicos especializados para mediciones in situ no destructivas en patrimonio cultural.

https://www.cope.es/actualidad/sociedad/noticias/conservacion-los-fosiles-arino-teruel-protagoniza-una-investigacion-multidisciplinar-varias-instituciones-20230531_2739167

<https://www.diariodeteruel.es/teruel/la-fundacion-dinopolis-lidera-una-investigacion-sobre-la-conservacion-de-los-fosiles-de-arino>

<https://www.que.es/2023/05/31/conservacion-fosiles-arino-teruel-protagoniza-investigacion-multidisciplinar-varias-instituciones/>

<https://www.dinopolis.com/prensa/la-conservacion-de-los-fosiles-de-arino-teruel-motivo-de-una-investigacion-multidisciplinar-de-varias-instituciones-aragonesas.html>

https://twitter.com/AragonNoticias_/status/1664308326090375168?t=HzhB0bGjqeDi0D349tUZCw&s=08

- Bringing Back to Life the Ariño Dinosaur Fossils in Spain”. The Cyprus Institute website, In Focus News: <https://www.cyi.ac.cy/index.php/in-focus/bringing-back-to-life-the-arino-dinosaur-fossils-in-spain.html>

- “Bringing Back to Life the Ariño Dinosaur Fossils in Spain”. APAC Laboratories, News: <https://apalabs.cyi.ac.cy/news/arino-dinosaur-fossils/>
- Repost on on Andreas Pittas Art Characterization Laboratories (APAC Labs) LinkedIn page: https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7082997599091273728?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- The news were also shared in the Cyprus Institute and Science and Technology for Archaeology and Culture social media (e.g., Facebook, Instagram).

- “Unlocking the Mysteries of Ancient Andean Wooden Boards: A Multidisciplinary Journey at the Museo delle Culture of Milan (MUDEC)”. The Cyprus Institute website, In Focus News:

<https://www.cyi.ac.cy/index.php/in-focus/unlocking-the-mysteries-of-ancient-andean-wooden-boards-a-multidisciplinary-journey-at-the-museo-delle-culture-of-milan-mudec.html>

- “Unlocking the Mysteries of Ancient Andean Wooden Boards: A Multidisciplinary Journey at the Museo delle Culture of Milan (MUDEC)”. APAC Laboratories, News: <https://apalabs.cyi.ac.cy/news/analysis-of-ancient-andean-wooden-board/>
- Post on Andreas Pittas Art Characterization Laboratories (APAC Labs) LinkedIn page: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/apac-laboratories_apalabs-cyprusinstitute-heritagescience-activity-7112736285034713088-00qL?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

- The news were also shared in the Cyprus Institute and Science and Technology for Archaeology and Culture social media (e.g., Facebook, Instagram).

Radio interview to E. Cano (MOLAB.es), program "A hombros de gigantes" Radio Nacional de España, "Laboratorio móvil para conservar el Patrimonio Cultural", 19/07/2023
<https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/a-hombros-de-gigantes/mas-cerca-laboratorio-movil-para-conservacion-del-patrimonio-cultural-metalico-19-07-23/6937632/>

≡ audio a hombros de gigantes

A HOMBROS DE GIGANTES

Laboratorio móvil para conservar el Patrimonio Cultural

19/07/2023 10:15

La corrosión de los metales es un gran problema al que no lo hemos dado la importancia que se merece por el elevado coste que supone para la sociedad. Y en particular, la degradación del patrimonio cultural metálico. Investigadores del Centro Nacional de Investigaciones Metalúrgicas (CENIM/CSIC) han desarrollado un laboratorio móvil que mide "in situ" el estado de los monumentos de forma que se pueda actuar en su preservación. En "Más cerca" (Radio 5) hemos entrevistado a **Emilio Cano**, doctor en Bellas Artes e investigador del CENIM.

rne

Publications of scientific literature include:

- Tornari, V ; Andrianakis, M ; Duchêne, S; Nowik, W; Brissaud, D ; Giovannacci, D; Kueppers, M ; Rehorn, C ; Blüemich, B ; Ricci, G; Artioli, G, A combined ND diagnostic investigation by DHSPI, SIRT, NMR, THZ, on Giotto fresco, Journal of Cultural Heritage, 63 (2023) 206-216 doi: [10.1016/j.culher.2023.07.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2023.07.021)
- L. Monico et al. Luminescent Inorganic Pigments Used in Ancient and Modern Times, In Molecular Luminescence in Cultural Heritage, Aldo Romani, Austin Nevin, Daniela Comelli and Maria J. Melo (eds.), 2022, Springer Ser Fluoresc, https://doi.org/10.1007/4243_2022_43
- L. Monico et al. Deeper insights into the photoluminescence properties and (photo)chemical reactivity of cadmium red (CdS_{1-x}Se_x) paints in renowned twentieth century paintings by state-of-the-art investigations at multiple length scales,
- Claudio Costantino, Letizia Monico, Francesca Rosi, Riccardo Vivani, Aldo Romani, Luis Carlos Colacho Hurtarte, Eduardo Villalobos-Portillo, Christoph J. Sahle, Thomas Huthwelker, Catherine Dejoie, Manfred Burghammer, Marine Cotte, *Non-destructive and Non-invasive Approaches for the Identification of Hydroxy Lead-Calcium Phosphate Solid Solutions [(Pb_xCa_{1-x})₅(PO₄)₃OH] in Cultural Heritage Materials*", Applied Spectroscopy, accepted March 2024, manuscript ID ASP-23-0391
- Selma Mayda, Letizia Monico, Dileep Krishnan, Steven De Meyer, Marine Cotte, Jan Garrevoet, Gerald Falkenberg, Irina CA Sandu, Bart Partoens, Dirk Lamoen, Aldo Romani, Costanza Miliiani, Johan Verbeeck, and Koen Janssens "A Combined Experimental and Computational Approach to Understanding CdS Pigment Oxidation in a Renowned Early 20th Century Painting." Chemistry of Materials 35, no. 24 (2023): 10403-10415.

- Avranovich Clerici, Ermanno, Steven De Meyer, Frederik Vanmeert, Stijn Legrand, Letizia Monico, Costanza Miliani, and Koen Janssens. "Multi-Scale X-ray Imaging of the Pigment Discoloration Processes Triggered by Chlorine Compounds in the Upper Basilica of Saint Francis of Assisi." *Molecules* 28, no. 16 (2023): 6106.
- Monico, Letizia, Francesco d'Acapito, Marine Cotte, Koen Janssens, Aldo Romani, Giulia Ricci, Costanza Miliani, and Laura Cartechini. "Total electron yield (TEY) detection mode Cr K-edge XANES spectroscopy as a direct method to probe the composition of the surface of darkened chrome yellow ($\text{PbCr}_{1-x}\text{S}_x\text{O}_4$) and potassium chromate paints." *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 539 (2023): 141-147.
- Magdalena Iwanicka, Patrizia Moretti Kathrin Pilz, Brenda Doherty, Laura Cartechini, Muriel Geldof, Suzan de Groot, Costanza Miliani and Piotr Targowski. "Congregation leaving the Reformed Church in Nuenen by Vincent van Gogh: a combined multi-instrumental approach to analyse the painting's stratigraphy in support of varnish removal" *Heritage Science* (2022) 10:167 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-022-00789-0>
- Alunni Cardinali, M., Cartechini, L., Paolantoni, M., Miliani, C., Fioretto, D., Pensabene Buemi, L., Comez, L., Rosi, F. (2022). Microscale mechanochemical characterization of drying oil films by in situ correlative Brillouin and Raman spectroscopy. *Science Advances*, 8(26), eabo4221.
- Brunetti, B. G., Cartechini, L., Moretti, P., Rosi, F., Iwanicka, M., & Miliani, C. (2022). In Situ Non-Invasive Analytical Techniques to Monitor the Cleaning of Painting Surfaces: A Review. *CONSERVATION 360^e*, (2).
- Isabella Baldini, Carla Sfameni, Lara De Giorgi, Ivan Ferrari, Francesco Giuri, Chiara Torre, Giovanni Leucci, 2023. Geophysical investigation at "Villa del Casale" Piazza Armerina (EN). Proceedings international conference metrology for archaeology and cultural heritage (Roma 19-21 ottobre 2023) pag 64-68, ISBN: 9789299009062
- Vincenzo Di Fiore, Michele Punzo, Daniela Tarallo, Maria Elisa Amadasi, **Giovanni Leucci**, 2023. Geophysical surveys at the Roman Aqueduct "Aqua Virgo"(Roma, Italy). Proceedings international conference metrology for archaeology and cultural heritage (Roma 19-21 ottobre 2023) pag 1050-1055, ISBN: 9789299009062
- A. Dal Fovo, S. Mattana, P. Riitano, A. Ramat, R. Cicchi, R. Fontana. "Insights into the stratigraphy and palette of a painting by Pietro Lorenzetti through non-invasive methods". *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 61 (2023) 91–99, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2023.03.002>
- A. Dal Fovo, L. Sepiacchi, S. Innocenti, J. Striova, R. Fontana "Botticelli-style tempera portrait on tile: Imaging and specific on-site spectroscopic analysis and cleaning examination". *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 66 (2024) 229–235; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2023.11.023>
- A. Dal Fovo, S. Mattana, C. Ruberto, L. Castelli, A. Ramat, P. Riitano, R. Cicchi, R. Fontana. Title: "Novel integration of non-invasive imaging techniques for the analysis of an egg tempera painting by Pietro Lorenzetti". *EPJ Plus*, 138(1), 71
- A. Dal Fovo, M. Martinez-Weinbaum, M. Oujja, M. Castillejo, R. Fontana. "Reflectance Spectroscopy as a Novel Tool for Thickness Measurements of Paint Layers". *Molecules* 2023, 28, 4683. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28124683>
- S. Innocenti, M. Ricci, D. Quintero Balbas, R. Fontana, J. Striova, M. Becucci "Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy for madder lake detection in painting layers" *Eur. Phys. J. Plus* (2023) 138:381 <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/s13360-023-03964-9>

- C. Riminesi, R. Manganelli Del Fa, S. Brizzi, A. Rocco, R. Fontana, M. Bertasa, E. Grifoni, A. Impallaria, G. Leucci, L. De Giorgi, I. Ferrari, F. Giuri, S. Penoni, A. Felici “Architectural assessment of wall paintings using a multimodal and multi-resolution diagnostic approach: The test site of the Brancacci chapel in Firenze” *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 66 (2024) 99–109
- Papadopoulos, N., Violante, C., Oikonomou, D., and Kritikakis, G., 2023. Coastal and shallow marine geophysical investigations in the Roman site of Baia in Naples, Italy. *Proceedings of 2023 Imeko International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage*, 908-912, ISBN 978-92-990090-6-2.
- T. Palomar, M. Iwanicka, I. Pombo Cardoso, M. Vilarigues, P. Targowski, "Assessing the decorative techniques of two Art Nouveau glass windows by optical coherence tomography (OCT)" *Heritage Science* 11(1), pp. 203, doi: 10.1186/s40494-023-01048-6, (2023)

2. MOLAB ACCESS ACTIVITIES (from M28)

2.1. Accessible techniques

MOLAB movable instruments, as listed in table 2, have been offered by the partnership of the 19 laboratories to the selected Users and managed in T4.3, in order to permit access campaigns to be carried out with no sampling and no contact on artworks, monuments or sites. All instruments were available this period, with the exception of instrumentation offered by MOLAB.fr (MNHN) 23. NIR hyperspectral imaging (900-2500nm) which suffered breakdown and was not repaired for the final duration.

Table 2: List of the MOLAB equipment per providing laboratory

Installation		Techniques provided within MOLAB
ID/No.	Short name	
MOLAB.it	CNR-SCITEC (UNIPG)	1 Total reflection mid/near-FTIR; Raman (λ_{exc} 785 & 1064nm)
		2 Raman (λ_{exc} 532nm); Macro XRF mapping; X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF)
		3 high resolution digital microscopy; (UV-VIS-NIR reflectance
		4 UV-VIS fluorescence; UV-VIS fluorescence time-decay
		5 Reflection VIS hyperspectral imaging (400-900 nm)
6 UV-Vis induced fluorescence hyperspectral imaging (400-900 nm))		
	CNR-ISPC@CT	7 PIXE/ low energy XRF
		8 Confocal XRF mapping
		9 Micro-XRF mapping;
		10 XRD mapping
	CNR-ISPC@PZ	11 Aerial remote sensing (UAV - RGB+Multispectral imagery)
		12 Aerial remote sensing (UAV - IRT imagery)
		13 Aerial remote sensing (LiDAR)
	CNR-ISPC@LE	14 Fluxgate gradiometry,
		15 Ground Penetrating Radar - medium and high frequency antenna
	CNR-INO	16 Scanning multispectral VIS-NIR reflectography;

		17 Optical profilometry
MOLAB.fr	CNRS(C2RMF)	18 Hyphenate XRD/XRF; 19 Hyphenate LIBS/LIF/Raman; 20 NIR hyperspectral imaging (900-2500 nm)
	(LRMF)	21 Terahertz imaging; 22 Thermography
	(MNHN)	23 NIR hyperspectral imaging (900-2500 nm)
MOLAB.pl	NCU	24 Optical Coherence Tomography (1960 nm)
MOLAB.gr	FORTH-IESL	25 Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DHSPI)
	FORTH-IMS	26 Laser scanning, total station and GPS; 27 Electrical Resistivity Tomography; 28 soil resistivity and conductivity techniques; 29 magnetic susceptibility measurements
	FORTH-Of ADC	30 Acoustic tomography
MOLAB.pt	UEVORA	31 Cytometer, 32 DNA and RNA sequencer, 33 luminometer lumitester, 34 PCR and electrophoresis system
MOLAB.es	CSIC	35 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
MOLAB.de	SPK-RWTH	36 NMR depth-profiling/relaxometry
MOLAB.ro	INOE	37 UAV Photogrammetry;
		38 3D structure-light scanner and 3D laser scanners
MOLAB.cy	CYI	39 Imaging methods for non-invasive dendrochronology
		40 3D modelling
MOLAB.uk	UCL-NTU	41 Remote VIS/NIR spectral imaging for rapid survey of large areas;
		42 Remote Vis/NIR/SWIR hyperspectral imaging;
		43 Remote Raman/LIF/LIBS spectroscopy;
		44 Optical Coherence Tomography (800 nm)

2.2. MOLAB Data Management

MOLAB has developed its own reporting system through task 4.4. As a preliminary solution, before implementing a final system compatible with DIGILAB tools, a pilot reporting system has been introduced and tested in collaboration with MOLAB providers (see inset- example of 4th Call project SYNTHETIC VARNISHES- providers MOLAB.pl; MOLAB.it; MOLAB.uk). To minimise compatibility problems, an XML-compliant MS Word document was developed in two versions: one for mobile objects and the other for heritage sites.

It has a hierarchical structure composed of the following high-level parts:

- a) Project general info, within tags: <ProjectData> </ProjectData> comprising essential information like project name, user leader, and project summary.
- b) Methodology, within tags: <Methodology1> ... </Methodology1> with tree structure comprising an identification of persons performing measurements, information on instrument properties, and conditions of examination and data processing. If more than one methodology (or instrument) was used by a given provider, this section is followed by: <Methodology2> ... </Methodology2> etc.
- c) Results section, a tree structure composed of:
 - i. Object info, comprising detailed information about the object under examination, within tags <Object1> ... </Object 1>. May be repeated as <Object2> ... </Object 2> if needed. This section is sent to the user leader to be filled out and distributed among all service providers **before** the examination campaign. It comprised information about the object's properties, condition, former alterations, examinations, and restorations. It also comprises information about copy/IP rights to all material attached to this section, including images of the object. In the case of heritage sites, another structure of this part is used and modified accordingly.
 - ii. The detailed results section is not structured as an XML document due to the various formats of results, depending on the given examination methodology. However, it must provide a reference (location, conditions, file name, etc.) to all examinations performed.
- d) The conclusions section comprises conclusions driven by all examination methods applied by a given provider. It is advisable that this section be supplemented in the future with conclusions from the entire campaign and references to publications resulting from the campaign.

MOLAB Transnational Access programme within the EU H2020 Project IPERION HS, contract no. 871034.

MOLAB Transnational Access Report

Call 4 10-10-2023

Project Title: Can deteriorated synthetic varnishes be removed from sensitive modern paint films such as acrylic emulsions and polyvinyl acetates using novel cleaning methods?

Acronym: Synthetic varnishes

User Leader (Name): Laura Homer

MOLAB Provider(s): Nicolaus Copernicus University in Torun, Poland

Access dates on site and place of examination: 22-25.08.2023, National Museum of Art (Nasjonalgalleriet, Nasjonalmuseet for Kunst, Oslo), Oslo, Norge

Access provided by: Piotr Targowski and Magdalena Iwanicka

Report prepared by: Magdalena Kowalska, Piotr Targowski

with Objects descriptions provided by: Laura Homer

Toruń, PL, 2023

This way, the report constitutes a complete document, searchable by metadata and providing comprehensive information about the conducted examination.

2.3. Call of proposals (July 2022- March 2024)

Within the period, two calls of proposals have been published under the MOLAB TNA programme, with the following deadlines:

- 30th September 2022 (fifth call),
- 28th February 2023 (sixth call).

2.4. Process steps

The entire evaluation and assessment of proposals submitted for MOLAB TNA access incorporates the following steps:

Step 1 – Information

Informative details are provided and updated on the IPERION HS website communicated also through the UserHelpdesk and the MOLAB helpdesk and through direct contact with the facility provider. For application optimization, potential Users are invited to request technical and scientific advice where applicable.

Step 2 – Submission

Proposers submitted their proposal through the single online entry point (using the MOLAB Application form once registered on the website), selecting the specific set of applicable instruments from the catalogue of services.

Step 3 – MOLAB providers technical feasibility assessment

Following the deadline of each Call, within a 2 week deadline, providers supply an initial assessment of only each individual project submitted requesting their specific facility and techniques. Each proposal on the dashboard could be deemed technically feasible or unfeasible where requested experimental techniques are considered appropriate or not, together with specific comments relating to scientific interest in the project. Important questions regarding specific logistics or health and safety aspects are made and communicated to the proposer.

Step 4 – Peer-Review Evaluation

Feasible applications are then transferred to the MOLAB *Peer Review Panel* in order to evaluate the scientific content of the project and rank the proposals according to implemented TNA ranking guidelines. The selection is based on the project *scientific quality*, following the principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality according to the sum of a weighted multi-criterion analysis. Specific weighted criteria include: 1/*scientific excellence*, 2/*Assessment of the state of the art of the topic and of the advancements of the field*, 3/*valorization and dissemination plan* 4/*expertise of User group*, 5/*Potential impact* as well as 6/*dissemination plan*.

Step 5 – Final decision

The provisional ranking of results of the M-PRP assessments are reported and discussed during each M-PRP meeting chaired by WP4 Coordinator, Costanza Miliani and in attendance also with the MOLAB representative T4.2 (Access provision management). Each meeting is finalized with the agreed listing of selected successful projects, projects to be strengthened and re-submitted and unsuccessful projects. Applicants are duly notified on insertion of results into the dashboard by automatic e-mail. Conclusions of the Peer Review process together with specific comments can be given to the User group leader on reasonable request to the helpdesk.

Step 6 – Timing and access modality

Access is allocated according to availability of the instrument in the requested period and any specific User needs. For each access campaign, a MOLAB team leader is identified by T4.2 who has the role to contact the Users Group Leader and plan the modality and extent of the access in accordance with each provider (days, period, logistics etc.). The MOLAB unit of access is defined per day. The work to be developed includes: (i) preparatory work, (ii) transport of the equipment to site, (iii) use of portable equipment and (iv) preliminary processing/interpretation of the acquired data. Each project is undoubtedly of variable duration depending on the nature and complexity of the specific research under study. Typically, each on-site intervention is expected to last maximum 5 days per provider.

Step 7 – Users duties

Each User Group Leader is ultimately reminded via an automatic e-mail from the dashboard on access completion to complete and upload the User Report on his/her MOLAB access' experiments within 2 months following MOLAB TNA access. Excerpts of the MOLAB User Reports are published in the IPERION website.

2.5. Outline of MOLAB Peer Review Panel activity

5th Peer Review Panel Meeting

The fifth M-PRP meeting was held virtually on 22nd December 2022 (11-13:00 CET). The following PRP members were present: Alison Heritage, Elsa Bourguignon and Marc Walton. Apologies were sent by Arianna Traviglia whose scores were via e-mail prior to the meeting. The meeting was chaired by the WP4 Coordinator, Costanza Miliani. A report of the minutes was compiled containing the results of the assessment and a copy was distributed by e-mail and signed for the final approval of all the PRP members.

At the fifth call, 10 proposals (Appendix I for list) were received from Austria [2], Lebanon [1], Italy [2], Belgium [1], France [1], Malta [1], Switzerland [1] and Sweden [1]. Following the feasibility assessment by the requested MOLAB providers, 10 feasible proposals were passed to the M-PRP for evaluation.

Of these applications, 2 proposals were accepted for MOLAB TNA (CALPIA- 1st ranking and AnBoMUDEC- 5th ranking), corresponding to a total of 10 access campaigns to be carried out by MOLAB.gr [1], MOLAB.it [ISPC_a-1; SCITEC-1; INO-1; UNIPG-1;], MOLAB.fr [1], MOLAB.pl [1], MOLAB.cy [1], MOLAB.de [1] and MOLAB.pt [1].

The applicants of the successful projects were notified by the dashboard. It was underlined that some providers have been highly requested during the IPERION HS project, for which there has been a clear saturation of their slots promised. In turn, projects ranking from 2nd to 4th position whose objectives also relied heavily on the instrumentation with no remaining slots could not be satisfied in this call. This has justified the 5th ranking project to gain TNA because it had requested providing facilities with completely available slots. See Table 3 for summary/appendix II for details.

6th Peer Review Panel

The sixth PRP meeting was held virtually on 2nd May 2023, (9-10am Rome time). The following PRP members were present: Alison Heritage, Elsa Bourguignon and Marc Walton and the meeting chaired by the WP4 Coordinator Costanza Miliani. Apologies were sent by Arianna Traviglia whose scores were via e-mail prior to the meeting. A report of the minutes was compiled containing the results of the assessment and a copy was distributed by e-mail and signed for the final approval of all the PRP members.

At this call, 11 proposals were received, 3 resubmissions and 1 continuation project from User Group Leaders of 7 different countries Austria [1], France [3], Greece [1], Bulgaria [2] Spain [1], Egypt [1], and Belgium [1]. Following the feasibility assessment by the MOLAB providers, 10 feasible proposals (Appendix 1 for list) were passed to the M-PRP for evaluation, 5 of which were selected for access (Salvator Mundi, CDHA, ICARE, MAP Philip the Good and PANDOSIA). The remaining 5 projects were unsuccessful given that this was the last call. See Table 3 for summary/appendix II for details

Table 3 - Summary of the selection activities during the reporting period to M48 (MOLAB PRP)

Call (deadline)	Date of M-PRP Virtual Meeting	No. of <i>feasible</i> Proposals evaluated	Countries	Overview of evaluation of proposals
5th Call (30 th September 2022)	5 th M-PRP meeting: 22 nd December 2022 11- 13.00 CET	10	AT (x2), LB, IT (x2), BE, FR, MT, CH, SE	2 successful_Selected for Access, 4 invited to re-submit 4 unsuccessful_not selected for Access
6th Call (28 th February 2023)	6 th M-PRP meeting: 2 nd May 2023 9- 10:00 CET	10	AT, FR (x3), GR, BG (x2), ES (x2), EG, BE	5 successful_Selected for Access 5 unsuccessful_not selected for Access

2.6. Transnational Access: Executed projects and KPIs

In the following, the projects implemented during from M28-M48 by the MOLAB providers are briefly described. The description includes the work developed, the days of access by each partner, the objectives of the measurements and the main results achieved.

In the final two Calls that have taken place, MOLAB received a total of 21 proposals, of which 20 proposals were considered feasible and were evaluated by the M-PRP: 10 relative to the fifth deadline of 30th September 2022; and 10 proposals from the sixth 28th February 2023. Of these proposals, 2 were selected for MOLAB TNA from the fifth PRP selection and 5 from the fourth PRP selection (Appendix II).

KPI_{Demand}

number of requests/ available slots for MOLAB targeted at ≥ 1.2 at 12 months having an average of 2.5 at M48

KPI_{E01}. Yearly number of Users requests MOLAB: in 2022 (4th and 5th Calls) received requests from 477 Users and in 2023 (6th Call) received requests from 166 users.

KPI_{E02}. Yearly number of granted accesses MOLAB in 2022 granted 7 projects comprising 22 access campaigns for providers and in 2023 granted 5 projects with 13 access campaigns.

Within the entire IPERION HS project 21 project proposals were selected for access spanning across 6 competitive Calls for access. 5 projects were completely carried out and described in deliverable D4.1 (CH_MPPM, NIBOTRAP, MRSL, GRANJA and BelMOD) which involved 17 access campaigns by MOLAB providers. The remaining 16 projects that have been executed with 55 access campaigns are summarized in table 3, where the title of the project, the number of days of access, the objectives of the measurements and details of scientific outputs are subsequently reported.

KPI_{Usersupport}: 0.83

Target ≥ 0.80 at 18 months
 From User satisfaction survey:
 Practical information on how to apply
 as well as the scientific and technical
 advice available from the User
 helpdesk

KPI_{feedback} : 0.87

Target ≥ 0.80 at 12 months after first
 access
 From User satisfaction survey:
 Overall fulfillment of expectations

2.6.1 Scientific output of Executed Projects

Among the results of experiments performed by the Users supported by this Grant Agreement through MOLAB, highlights of each concluded project are given, to show how essential the MOLAB movable equipment is for European research teams and projects in the cultural heritage field. Details of the User groups and researchers involved in each project are listed in the table in appendix III

1st CALL Project

Project Title: OCT, 3D structure -light scanner and integrated XRD-XRF applied to conservation dinosaurs fossils with pyrite decay and evaluation of innovate method conservation (PYRITEDINOSAUR)

User Group Leader: Nuria Miguel (group leader)

Venue: Palaeontological Network Foundation of Teruel-Dinópolis (FCPTD)-Dinópolis Av. de Sagunto, 44001 Teruel, Spain

Pyrite decay, also referred to as pyrite disease or pyrite decay, is one of the most serious problems faced in paleontological conservation. Although the details of the degradation mechanism are still under investigation most authors now agree on the fact that the decay involves the oxidation of sulphide to sulphate species. Typically, they appear as yellowish or grey/white powder that covers the surface of the specimen and has a sulphurous odour associated. Critically, the transformation from sulphide to sulphate induces a significant volume increase, which eventually results in the specimen cracking and breakage. The damage is irreversible and pyritized fossils often break down very quickly, even to the point of complete destruction. The sulphuric acid produced by the oxidation and hydration may also degrade labels, storage cardboard boxes and wooden furniture (Newman,1998). This multidisciplinary project involves a comprehensive study on the specific degradation of the Ariño fossils using the following in situ non-destructive (without sampling) analytical techniques requested as part of MOLAB: - **Integrated XRD-XRF and LIBS** from MOLAB.fr to determine the different phases (chemical composition and crystal structure) and the description of the microstructure (grain size, texture) of the pyritized fossils. - **3D structure-light scanner (SLS) and Photogrammetric technique (PH)** from MOLAB.cy to monitor structural changes based on environmental and climatic change. Deformation and fracture mechanisms will be investigated to

evaluate the structural condition of fossils and obtain a 3D graphic document of fossils with pyrite decay, which will be used for its documentation, dissemination and reproduction if necessary. 3D models allow accurate measurements of the geometry of the specimens, improved visualisation of their textural details and quantitative shape analysis operations. • Scientific objectives of the visit - Conduct a comprehensive study on the oxidation processes of pyrite in fossils from the Mina Santa María de Ariño site under various environmental conditions. 1. Study fossils at varying stages of pyrite degradation. 2. Characterise fragmented fossil to understand the different materials observed in the stratigraphy of the fossil. 3. Characterise fossils after treatment with Regalrez and Paraloid. 4. Examine the presence of efflorescences found on fossils. - Obtain a 3D graphic document of fossils with pyrite decay, which will be used for its documentation, dissemination and reproduction if necessary. - Contribute to the dissemination, appreciation, and preservation of this significant Aragonese heritage on a global scale. - Encourage interdisciplinary collaboration among diverse and complementary institutions such as education and research. - Provide opportunities for students and grant recipients to train with this extraordinary collection and with an interdisciplinary team committed to achieving excellence in academic instruction.

Integrated XRD-XRF and LIBS has allowed the characterization of the main materials related to pyrite disease: determination of the different phases (chemical composition, crystal structure). - 3D structure-light scanner (SLS) and Photogrammetric technique (PH) has allowed investigating and evaluating the structural condition of fossils and obtaining a 3D graphic document of fossils with pyrite decay, which will be used for its documentation, dissemination and reproduction if necessary. The 3D models will allow accurate measurements of the geometry of the specimens, improved visualisation of their textural details and quantitative shape analysis operations.

2nd CALL Project

Project Title: Diagnostics for conservation at Müstair Monastery (DIACOMM)

User Group Leader Patrick Cassiti (group leader)

Venue: Convent Church of St. John, Müstair, Switzerland

The monastery church of St. John is one of very few sites in Europe which preserve 8th century wall paintings. The extension and good conditions of these paintings is unique. Since the early 1980s deterioration processes affecting the wall paintings have been subjected to diagnostic investigations. The publications resulting from these studies illustrate the preventive and passive approach adopted to manage deterioration related to soluble salts activities in concomitance with extreme and fluctuating climatic conditions. These and other studies, now several decades old, have provided information on the painting technology but most importantly have shown that the restoration carried out from 1947–51 has caused the deterioration of the paintings. A major factor was the heating installed in the church in the 1950s. The situation was stabilized with the removal of the heating in 1987 and the dry cleaning of the wall paintings. Regular close-up controls and monitoring of the surface condition showed that the deterioration is on-going even if considerably

slower. An as yet unidentified surface coating applied during the 1947–51 restoration probably plays an important part by binding dust from the air and reducing humidity movement through the surface. A research project carried out 2000–2005 investigated the varnish layer, which covers the wall paintings. While it was not possible to determine its composition, it was found that it acts as a substrate for the growth of microorganisms, that it binds dirt to the surface, and that it loses elasticity over time, becoming less soluble. It was not possible, with the analytical methods of the time, which were all invasive in nature, to determine the composition of this surface coating. While an intervention was not deemed to be urgent, the coating was identified as a threat for the wall paintings, especially in case of a change of the microclimate. A section of the northern wall of the monastery church with a surface of c. 20 m² has been designated as the study area where paintings had not been subjected to any treatment since the restoration of 1947–51. The area includes different surfaces: 8th century plaster and wall-paintings, 15th century plasters covered with whitewash, and gypsum plasters from the 1947–51 restoration, which also added a layer of fixatives and overpaintings which covers all surfaces. This complex situation can be regarded as representative for most other areas inside the church. A stable scaffolding will be erected to allow better access to the wall.

The work with the MOLAB teams (Italy, France, UK, Germany and Greece), was planned in a systematic manner with the objective of making the most from the investigation, allowing data integration and following a strict methodological approach. The methods chosen for the project complement each other and promise a maximum information gain. The proposed work began with remote and imaging techniques followed by point analysis on areas selected on the base of the results obtained. The project worked to identify areas with different acoustic/thermal/magnetic behaviour to identify those corresponding to detachment or loss of cohesion. The mapping technique was used to define the measurement spots for the point analysis. The individuation of hollow/less cohesive areas will be of importance, showing the conservation conditions of the medieval cycle, provides a starting point for planning any intervention campaign. The identification of moisture and salt content of the walls, even if only superficially, also provides useful insights into the condition of the paintings as well as risk factors and damage mechanisms. The investigation of the stratigraphy and the chemical characterization of the paint layers (both original and repaintings) are necessary for the formulation of hypotheses concerning the decay processes they may be involved in.

3rd CALL Project

Project Title: Evaluation of Protection for Heritage Aircraft (EPHA)

User Group Leader Elodie Guilminot (group leader)

Venue: Arc Antique Laboratory, Nantes, France

Images in inset- C.Colonnier©, Arc'Antique - Grand Patrimoine de Loire Atlantique

Even though the Second World War (WWII) is often considered the golden age of military aviation and the WWII aircraft heritage has an undeniable historical and emotional value, only recently these remains have officially entered the field of archaeology and cultural heritage conservation, making their presence in national museums somewhat limited. This massive confrontation caused considerable human and material losses, leaving many remains on European soil and in the sea that, in most cases, are cared by volunteers and associations. Besides, it is significant to recall that rescuing an aircraft wreck is challenging from several points of view, such as its history, legal statutes, condition, size, composition and materials. Considering this, the Protection and Conservation of Heritage Aircraft European project (PROCRAFT- JPICH) will face these challenges by connecting the multiple actors of the operational chain from recovery to exhibition. More than 21 scientists and associated partners (museums, associations, conservators, state representatives, mediators) from Italy, Czech Republic and France will benefit from their joint expertise and capabilities. One of the principal actions of PROCRAFT is to develop protective coatings for aircraft wrecks, according to conservation criteria and the requirements of European Health and Safety Regulations in terms of environmental compatibility. Besides, identifying its advantages, limits and comparing it with different traditional coatings. The protective coatings will be applied on three different real wrecks. A Supermarine Spitfire aircraft wing, the second, over the propeller blades of a P38 Lightning and the propeller blades found in Fécamp, French coast: In-situ electrochemical examinations by electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), and External reflection mid/near-FT-IR analyses were performed over these artefacts to evaluate the corrosion protection durability, thickness alteration, crack formation and degradation of the protective layers one year after their application. The interest of this analysis campaign was to be able to characterize the protections using different techniques, but these analyzes had to be carried out at the same time. One of the big challenges was finding a date on which all the teams could be present. During the October 2022 campaign, we were able to bring together the teams (MOLAB.it; MOLAB.uk; MOLAB.pl; MOLAB.es) who carried out FTIR, μ XRF, EIS, and OCT analyses. In addition to the data collected, all the teams were happy to meet up and share their know-how and in-situ measurement practices. This conviviality has forged links that have facilitated future exchanges, particularly for the valorization of results. We evaluated the corrosion protection of six different treatments one week after their application over real aircraft wrecks. However, for analyzing the lifetime efficiency and durability of these protection systems, it is necessary to study their surface condition and corrosion resistance after a prolonged exposure time, which will be the objective of our proposal for the 5th IPERION HS call.

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3rd CALL Project

Project Title: The Hunt Frieze of Tomb II at Vergina, Greece: A Novel Interdisciplinary Approach for the Scientific Investigation and Revisualization of a Painted Masterpiece of the Classical World (HFTV-ReVIS)

User Group Leader Hariclia Brecolaki (group leader)

Venue: Archaeological site of Aigai (Vergina, Greece), Museum of the Royal Tombs

The project was carried out by the National Hellenic Research Foundation, in collaboration with the National Centre for Scientific Research “Demokritos”, and the Hellenic Ministry of Culture and Sports. By getting access in the research infrastructure of the MOLAB a great amount of new information on the hunt frieze was obtained, both regarding its painting materials and its iconography, considerably enriching our data on this unique painting. The HFTV-ReVis project highlights the key importance of interdisciplinarity and state-of-the-art technology in the art historical and archaeological study of the hunt frieze, which, owing to its exceptional quality and great historical significance, is the most renowned painting of classical antiquity. The HFTV-ReVis project focused on the non-invasive investigation of the hunt frieze, a 4th c. BC wall painting which adorns the Tomb of Philip II of Macedon at Vergina, Greece, discovered in 1977. The depicted scene, owing to its exceptional artistry and great historical significance, is the most renowned painting of classical antiquity, encapsulating as it does essential qualities of the tradition of mimetic representation. It is composed of different hunting episodes, involving groups of hunters and hounds attacking different species of prey, in an expansive landscape consisting of natural and human-made elements. A significant number of studies has been dedicated to the painted frieze and many speculations have been advanced regarding the hunt’s significance, its possible location, the eventual symbolism of the multiple quarries, the status of the hunters, and the identification of the protagonists with historical figures of the Macedonian court. Regrettably, however, the extensive weathering of its surface impeded a full appreciation of its great artistry and a thorough understanding of its iconography. It was therefore extremely important to preserve the existing evidence by documenting and investigating properly all the remaining pictorial layers.

The scientific objectives of HFTV-ReVis project were a) to get information on the exact composition of the colours (pigments and binders), the texture and depth of the paint layers and b) to bring to light specific iconographic elements from the hunt frieze which nowadays are not perceivable to the naked eye due to the poor state of the pictorial surface. The robust scientific evidence generated would offer a substantial quantity of “objective” data on which an accurate colour reconstruction of the original painting could rely on, hopefully allowing us to overcome the danger of misinterpretations and to minimize the window of error probability. An extensive non-invasive, in situ investigation of the painting using state-of-the-art equipment offered by the MOLAB, not hitherto accessible in Greek institutions, seemed as the most appropriate means in order to obtain the maximum of data on the surface of the painting. The reason for choosing IPERION HS facilities was determined by both the quality and quantity of the offered services,

combining the most advanced methods and technologies for in situ measurements with experts in the field of non-invasive investigation of cultural heritage. The two phases of the campaign included the in-situ implementation of different photographic methods and spectroscopic non-invasive analytical techniques providing complementary elemental, molecular and crystalline phase characterization of the hunt frieze's colour palette, along with the evaluation and interpretation of the findings. The applied techniques were the following: 1. Photographic techniques, XRAYLab CNR-ISPC 2. Fiber Optics Reflectance Spectroscopy (FORS), CNR-SMAArt 3. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), CNR-SMAArt 4. X-ray Diffraction (XRD) mapping and point analysis, XRAYLab CNR-ISPC 5. Macroscopic X-ray Fluorescence (MA-XRF) imaging spectrometry, XRAYLab CNR-ISPC 6. VNIR Hyperspectral Imaging, CNR-SMAArt 7. Remote VNIR spectral imaging VNIR (VNIR-SI), NTU-ISAAC 8. Remote SWIR Hyperspectral Imaging (SWIR-HSI), NTU-ISAAC 9. Remote VNIR Hyperspectral Imaging (VNIR-HSI), NTU-ISAAC 10. Remote LIF Hyperspectral Imaging (LIF-HSI) NTU-ISAAC. The methodology initiated with extensive imaging and mapping techniques, including VIL (applied by G. Verri) and MA-XRF, which played a pivotal role in identifying areas suitable for subsequent point XRD, FORS and FTIR analyses. VIL identified the Egyptian Blue pigment in both blue and light blue hues by its strong luminescence in NIR region. Further on, VIL and MA-XRF imaging have revealed that in some areas the Egyptian Blue has been mixed or overpainted with a CU/As based green pigment. The very significant results and high amount of data obtained through the MOLAB expedition in Vergina need to be further elaborated, discussed and understood in order to definitely conclude on the exact gamut of materials used in the hunt frieze, their distribution and eventual degradation/alteration.

3rd CALL Project

Project Title: Integrating on-land and shallow marine geophysical investigations to detect buried archeological features in a coastal area. The Roman site of Baiae, Phlegrean Fields Archaeological Park (Naples, Italy) (SuBaiae)

User Group Leader: Dr. Fabio Pagano (group leader)

Venue: Phlegrean Fields Archaeological Park, Naples, Italy

The proposed Molab activity aimed to fill the gap of data in the very shallow water and onshore environments of the submerged site of Baiae. In particular the activity included: 1) dynamic and static 3-D Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) to examine the sedimentary layers below the seabed and 2) Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) to check the continuation of remains on the coast. Such integrated approach was expected to assess and implement non-destructive geophysical methods for archaeological applications at sea-land interface. The geophysical campaign on the coastal and shallow marine area in the bay of Baia has been performed as a demonstration study to indicate the effectiveness of the Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR), sonar bathymetry, static and dynamic electrical resistivity

Marine ERT and Sonar investigations

tomography (ERT) to fill the gap of data in the very shallow water and onshore environment of the submerged archaeological features. The survey was carried out in the period of 6-12 November 2022 and it was focused on the coast, the shallow and the relatively deeper sections of the bay. The bathymetric survey covered more than 19,000 square meters and it was conducted by combining two different methods depending on the thickness of the sea water. The coastal area and the shallower part of the bay was mapped using a Javad Triumph-1 GNSS unit mounted on a pole which

was in constant connection to a base station for differential corrections. For the deeper parts of the bay the SonarMite BTX single beam sonar was used. GPR covered 1,250 square meters along the coast with a 225MHz antenna taking measurements every 5cm along parallel transects 0.5m apart. The static ERT covered a grid of 40m x 47m (1,880 square meters) where the field strategy involved the collection of the resistivity data with the dipole-dipole array along 41 parallel 2D lines placed 1m apart, where the basic inter electrode spacing along each

traverse was also set to 1m. The deeper marine part was surveyed using the submerged dynamic ERT mode along ten partially parallel lines having a cumulative length of 1.08 Km that covered a marine area of about 12,500 square meters. The specific measuring mode employed a constantly moving dipole-dipole array along a predefined line where the multimode cable was submerged and attached to the seabed during the tomographic data collection. The data processing of the different geophysical measurements followed the basic flowchart. However an additional module was also incorporated in the processing chain of the static ERT data arising by the in situ observation of a substantial daily variation of around 40 cm in the sea level elevation. Thus in order to include this parameter in the inversion of the static resistivity data, the sea level was periodically monitored during the execution of the tomographic measurements in the different days. More specifically, the GNSS measurements in constant points showed a linear decrease of the sea elevation with time which was taken into account for the correction of the thickness of the water column. So for every ERT line the correct water column thickness was calculated by subtracting the elevation of the sea surface from the elevation of the seabed according to the time that the measurements of a given line were completed. The specific correction was not implemented in the dynamic ERT lines since the total measuring time was negligible with respect to the daily sea level changes. The GPR depth slices show a strong attenuation of the electromagnetic signal in the depths larger than 40-50cm, especially in the section that is closer to the coastline. Furthermore, the superficial slices outline some strong reflections along the western boundary of the GPR grid. The nature of these high reflectivity areas is twofold, originating from the increased moisture due to the flow of water along small streams and the accumulation of surface stones/pebbles. Thus, the existence of these external factors obscured any electromagnetic signal that could be attributed to potential subsurface archaeological features. The 3D resistivity inversion model of the static ERT grid exhibited relatively low RMS error

(8.2%) showing the good quality of the collected data. The submerged subsurface was divided in ten layers of progressively increasing thickness reaching up to the depth of 5.6 meters below the seabottom. The entire range of the respective depth slices outline a linear conductive feature with resistivity values less than 0.05 Ohm-m that is characteristic to a metallic object. It has an average thickness of 3.5m and an almost north-south orientation. Its visible length is more than 27m that seems to extend further to the south and outside the limits of the grid. The in situ visible observation of a metallic object on the seabed during the measurements and the information from the locals, it is reasonable to assume that this conductive linear feature is attributed to a collapsed funnel related to a shipwreck.

4th CALL Project

Project Title: The materiality of the Medieval North – the palette of Swedish and Finnish reconstructed Manuscripts (MoMNoPSAF)

User Group Leader Thea Winther (group leader)

Venue: Swedish National Archives, Sweden

The Latin book culture of medieval Sweden (containing present-day Finland) remains poorly known due to the challenges of the source material. The books of the church were recycled by the early-modern tax administration as binding material for tax accounts and exist today in collections of Nordic cultural institutions as so-called fragments, in numbers of well over 40 000 parchment leaves. Primarily traditional methods used in manuscript studies, such as palaeography and codicology, have been applied for the contextualisation of these objects. Less has been done by way of scientific analysis, therefore we turn our eyes to their materiality. By applying scientific methods, data that

further enables us to understand the manufacture, origin, and qualities of these fragments have been collected. The analyses have provided information of relevance to the history of craftsmanship, book culture, religious study, and trade, and for the Nordic context in particular, from the time of its recent integration into Christianity and Catholicism. Ten fragments dated to the 12th to the 15th century were studied by microscopy, hyperspectral imaging in visible light (385 – 1040 nm) and ultraviolet (UV) fluorescence, X-ray fluorescence, reflectance spectroscopy in the UV, visible and near infrared range (300-1600 nm), external reflectance in the mid- and near infrared and Raman spectroscopy. Pigments, colourants, and inks have been characterized and identified. The results reveal the presence of many of the materials commonly used in book production in Europe at the time, such as vermilion, red lead, azurite, orpiment and copper based greens, with some exceptions. The colourant components evince significant variation, and it appears likely that they were largely received via trade routes and learned networks from various European locations. The documents from the 12th century differ from the others in their substances and practices, such as the use of ultramarine for calendar rubrics and a varied use of different reds and greens. All fragments were scanned by macro-XRF and HSI. 136 FTIR spectra, 23 Raman spectra, 93 UV-VIS reflectance and 13 UV-VIS Fluorescence spectra were collected. μ -XRF mapping were conducted for eight details. The results of this study reveal the presence of many of the materials commonly used in European book production at the time, such as vermilion, red lead, azurite, orpiment, and copper-based greens,

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with some exceptions. Two fragments dated to the 12th century show different materials in comparison to others in the selection of fragments. They contain, for example, ultramarine used for the text in a calendar, a varied use of different reds and greens, and a tannin ink.

For the greens, both green earth and copper-based green are present. For red initials the presence of iron associated with particles of zinc, copper, and manganese can be seen. It has been possible to observe the use of a variety of materials for elements of manuscript production such as text, textual additions, musical notation, decorations, and images, within the same document, which suggests that many of the manuscripts were the result of collaborations by several different artisans. The study of the palette of these medieval Swedish manuscript pages has shown a complexity and a well-developed craftsmanship that reflect the developing book culture of high- and late-medieval Sweden. The colourant components of the studied selection evince significant variation, and it appears likely that they were received via trade routes and learned networks from various European destinations. The sample selection of fragments from ten books limits the level of generalisation possible and therefore, in order to see general trends more fragments would need to be studied. Further study of the colourants could be helpful in

trying to connect manuscripts with particular writing centres. The presence of particular impurities in colourants, were these to appear in several manuscripts, could be a particularly useful indicator. This study has also shown that these methods could contribute to the grouping of fragments by showing similarities or differences in materials. In particular, the presence of impurities can be useful for such examinations. While there are, of course, limitations in the determination of geographical origin by these methods alone, they offer an important addition to the more traditional methodological toolkit of manuscript studies and, especially, for the fragment studies.

4th CALL Project

Project Title: Can deteriorated synthetic varnishes be removed from sensitive modern paint films such as acrylic emulsions and polyvinyl acetates using novel cleaning methods? (Synthetic Varnishes)

User Group Leader Laura Homer (group leader)

Venue: National Museum of Art, Norway

The mobile laboratory, MOLAB (access provided by the EU-funded IPERION HS Programme), travelled to the National Museum of Norway to conduct a non-invasive, multimodal analytical study of ten acrylic and polyvinyl acetate (PVAc) paintings represented in the museum collection. The paintings are being used as case studies in a PhD research project in which the removability of commercial artists' varnishes is being investigated. Novel varnish removal methods will be tested on mock-ups that are based on materials used on real, case-study paintings. Identification, documentation and characterisation of the synthetic paints and varnishes present on the ten case study paintings. Identification and differentiation of single polymer and copolymer materials, acrylic-vinyl copolymers and pure acrylic resin (co)polymers, emulsions and solutions. Potential comparison with known commercial products from existing reference libraries and identification of specific brands used. Evaluation of the suitability of the different methods in assessing and

visualising the effectiveness of varnish removal tests on mock-up paint and varnish samples. Three teams, with four instruments, came, MOLAB.it came with single-point external reflection mid-IR spectroscopy (range 8000–400cm⁻¹). MOLAB.uk came with hybrid optical coherence tomography at 1300 nm with co-aligned spectral imaging (415–845 nm; with 10 nm bandwidth) and remote shortwave infrared hyperspectral imaging (SWIR-HSI; 1000–2500 nm). MOLAB.it came with optical micro-profilometry. MOLAB.pl with optical coherence tomography at 850 nm. MOLAB.gr came with ultrasonic acoustic tomography. All instruments were employed for measurements of all 10 case study paintings. In addition, mid-FTIR and OCT at 1300 nm with co-aligned spectral imaging were applied to mock up paint and varnish samples, before and after varnish removal tests. Remote shortwave infrared hyperspectral imaging was employed for single layer varnish paint outs. Acoustic tomography is a contact analytical method. This was not ideal for the valuable, original paintings, despite the method being developed to be used without a hydrogel coupling layer. The pressure required to get a good reading was problematic for the artworks. This method could be safely used on mock up paint and varnish samples. Unfortunately, images of the mid-FTIR locations were not captured and saved, which meant re-locating the exact spot locations was challenging for all subsequent instruments employed. Positive identification of the primary resin types of varnishes was possible with IR spectroscopy; in most cases acrylic and/or vinyl resin was detected. The combination with SWIR-HSI enabled imaging of the spatial distribution of the varnishes and binders. Distinctions between monomer and copolymer compositions were evaluated by comparison with reference materials. The thickness and number of varnish layers were resolved with OCT at both wavelengths, for all except one painting. Acoustic tomography showed promising results for the evaluation of varnish removal tests, by comparing images collected before and after. The findings enable appropriate and suitable mock-ups to be made, which are representative of existent paintings. This fulfills the main criteria of the MOLAB project. Evaluation of varnish removal tests using novel cleaning methods on these mock-ups can be more readily appropriated to real-life scenarios, ultimately supporting conservation decision-makers during the potential removal of these varnish layers from real paintings.

4th CALL Project

Project Title: Advanced diagnostic procedures for the informed restoration intervention on fresco wall paintings by Giotto, Bardi Chapel (Basilica Santa Croce, Florence, Italy) (GIOTTO@Bardi)

User Group Leader Antonina Chaban (group leader)

Venue: Bardi Chapel, Basilica Santa Croce, Florence, Italy

Fresco wall paintings in the Bardi Chapel of Santa Croce Basilica (Florence, Italy) have a complicated history. Realized by Giotto presumably between 1320 and 1326, these wall paintings were limewashed and some scenes were destroyed due to the integration of funeral monuments in the 18th - beginning of the 19th century. The subsequent restoration interventions, in 19th-20th centuries (uncovering of limewashed paintings, reintegrations and their removal, mortar refillings etc.) are known but poorly documented. In this new diagnostic and restoration project (2022-2024), we aim at optimizing the methodology to address issues of conservation state of the fresco wall paintings in the Bardi Chapel, by integrating the state-of-art non-invasive structural and physical-chemical characterization tools, suitable for the purpose. The selected methods of the Molab catalogue include DHSPI (Molab Greece), SIRT and THz Imaging (Molab France) and NMR depth profiling (Molab Germany). The specific MOLAB team expertise and the instrumental performance were crucial to obtain the missing subsurface structural information and to disclose further details on Giotto's painting technique and on its historical evolution, providing support to the ongoing restoration intervention. The selected MOLAB techniques operate with different physical principles, providing different types of complementary and high-resolution information on the conservation state and integrity of the fresco mortar and mortar/wall interface. Molab Greece and Molab France access was carried out in 2022-2023, while Molab Germany was not possible due to the changes in on-site logistics and time constrains. The measurements with the DHSPI system were performed in November 2022, while the measurements SIRT and THz imaging, complemented by 3d structural light scanner, were performed in May 2023. The measurements with DHSPI and SIRT covered all the regions of interest (ROIs) located on 4 distinct fresco wall painting scenes (total area of ROIs around 5-7 m² per each scene by Giotto), performing the measurements on the northern and on the southern wall of the Chapel from 2 different scaffold levels. The measurements by DHSPI and by SIRT were carried out on exactly the same areas of interest, using the same thermal excitation gradient (IR lamps) and cooling monitoring time (3-6 minutes). The measurement with THz system were carried out on two areas of interest, each ca. 20 x 30 cm, examined previously by DHSPI and SIRT. On all the areas, examined by DHSPI, SIRT and THz, complementary measurements by 3d structural light system were carried out. The Molab access help us advance the standard structural diagnostic procedures on this case study, discussed and analysed in collaboration with the Molab provider teams and interdisciplinary experts within the user group. The scientific approach by DHSPI-SIRT allowed not only the identification of defects (detachments, cracks etc.) in the fresco subsurface but also their future risk classification. It was possible to discuss and to determine, in collaboration with conservators-restorers, the areas of the wall paintings that require an immediate intervention (high risk) and those that might require attention in the future (low or future risk). The DHSPI-SIRT complementary approach allowed a holistic assessment of thermodynamic behaviour of the subsurface multi-layered fresco wall painting system in its complexity. Going into detail, the THz Imaging and Spectroscopy method made a significant contribution to this project through non-invasive subsurface stratigraphic analysis on the smaller

Photo 1: Southern wall inside the Bardi Chapel. Credits: "File:Bardi Visión.JPG" by Miguel Hermoso Cuesta is licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0.

Photo 2: Basilica di Santa Croce main façade. Florence, Italy. Credits: Laura Benassi

areas, identified through the initial full-field characterization by DHSPI and SIRT. The THz Imaging and Spectroscopy technique was used to detect discontinuities and to assess their in-depth location and dimensions, as well as to differentiate between pigments on the wall painting surface. The technique provided us also with the complementary information for the 3D surface topography reconstruction, supporting the 3d scanner data.

4th CALL Project

Project Title: Saving Industrial Metals (SIM)

User Group Leader David Thickett (group leader)

Venue: JW Evans Silver Factory, Birmingham, UK

Industrial sites form an important part of Europe's cultural heritage. The sites often have strong links with local communities and frequently attract volunteer custodians. The buildings often present challenging environments due to their nature and metal collections frequently undergo rapid deterioration once the site stops working. Coatings are essential to preserve this important heritage and waxes are often recommended due to the complex nature of the objects. Unfortunately, little scientific research has been published on the performance of these materials in such situations. This project would provide the first scientific assessment of the long term performance of the five most widely used coatings. J. W. Evans was saved for the nation in 2008. Established in 1881, J. W. Evans is one of the most complete surviving historic factories in Birmingham's Jewellery Quarter. To walk into the factory today is to enter a lost industrial world. As well as the extant machinery including drop and fly presses, it contains 161000 artefacts. After a literature search and discussion with conservators and institutions the five most widely used coatings were applied to steel dyes in 2010 and some of the machinery in 2018. These naturally aged coatings, in a well characterised environment, provide an ideal opportunity to assess their long term effectiveness. This assessment will be critical to inform other organisations caring for similar sites.

The nature of industrial buildings often means they have relatively aggressive environments with high RH and high levels of pollutant ingress. Some materials are exposed externally at maritime sites which generate very high corrosion rates of ferrous metals. Hence materials frequently require effective coatings to control corrosion rates. The effective lifetime of the coatings determines their likely impact. Industrial collections are frequently managed using volunteers with limited conservation time available. There has been little published scientific research on the performance of wax type coatings. These have several advantages and are often recommended by conservators working in this area. Some of the materials found to have performed best in previous testing are no longer available or require specialist application, beyond the resources of many organisations involved in caring for industrial heritage. Much of the research has relied on accelerated aging or relatively short exposure times. Whilst these provided comparative results, it is recognised in coating literature that there is frequently a disagreement between accelerated and natural aging and the relative performance of materials can

change with time. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy, EIS is regarded as a primary method for assessing coating efficacy and generates significant data rapidly. The move towards gel-based electrolytes has allowed its use on complex surfaces. This is particularly useful for vertical surfaces which are known to be problematic for even coating application. The machinery mainly has vertical surfaces. The gel also allows analysis with minimal disruption or interference to the coating, allowing further analyses. The reversibility of the coatings will be assessed after the project. X-ray diffraction and Raman spectroscopy are very well established for ferrous corrosion product.

5th CALL Project

Project Title: Rediscovery of Callisto Piazza master's art. A unique research opportunity during the restoration of the "Assumption and Coronation of the Virgin" panel painting in Lugano (CH) (CALPIA)

User Group Leader Corinna Ludovica, Koch Dandolo (group leader)

Venue: MASI Palazzo Reali, Lugano, Switzerland

Cantone Ticino, Lugano Municipality, and Lugano Diocese own the panel painting "The Assumption and Coronation of the Virgin" (1548-1551) by Callisto Piazza, originally part of a triptych located in Santa Maria degli Angeli Church (Lugano, Ticino, Switzerland). The art of Callisto Piazza has been re-evaluated in a relative recent time. Due to this late recognition, Callisto's artistic technique has never been characterized in depth. In fact, the definition of Callisto's art is mainly based on stylistic considerations and we note the lack of characterization from a technical and material point of view, by means of targeted and far-reaching diagnostic investigations. Thus, the motivation behind the MOLAB visit was in first place the characterization of Piazza original painting technique by means of a broad in-depth scientific examination, in order to establish a point of reference for future studies on this eminent artist. In addition, from a conservation point of view, the painting is showing a

critical situation in terms of overpainting and varnish stratification; therefore, it was expected that the MOLAB investigation would provide an in-depth characterization by means of mapping and reflection-spectroscopic techniques to plan and better address the cleaning intervention. The most controversial conservation phenomenon is the cracking of the painted surface, which is probably related to internal stresses in the wooden support. The MOLAB facilities for subsurface investigation, such as DHSPI-II, could have been used to

determine the origin and extent of this phenomenon, in order to assess the need of interventions on the wooden support or on the painting cradling placed on the back during a previous restoration intervention. The scientific objectives of the MOLAB visit were therefore: - to characterize the original painting technique of the Piazza through a broad in-depth scientific study; - to clarify the overpainting and varnish stratification found on the painting, to correctly address the cleaning intervention, by means of surface and depth profiling mapping techniques; - to understand the phenomenon of diffuse surface cracking by analyzing the wooden support using sub-surface imaging techniques. The Iperion HS MOLAB was chosen because of its wide range of cutting-edge analytical technologies, including spectroscopic, mapping and depth profiling techniques, as well as its extensive experience in approaching works of art and interpreting scientific data. Research groups involved included MOLAB.it, MOLAB.gr and MOLAB.pl.

Imaging devices in the VIS-NIR range provided an overall global view of the painting. Their spectral mapping capability helped to characterize the techniques used by the artist to trace and compose

the figures in the representation. It also helped to clarify the presence or absence of underdrawings and the distribution/extent of overpainting. Vis-NIR hyperspectral imaging helped to make an initial identification of surface pigments through end-member extraction. UV hyperspectral analysis clarified the absence of organic dyes/lacquer glazes. XRF and XRD analyses have deepened the understanding of the pigment composition at the elemental level and their distribution through elemental mapping. Gold mapping has helped to identify the original gilding design, which is currently almost lost. Pb mapping has revealed the presence of hidden figures and details that were later covered over by the artist for the final composition. OCT analysis has identified the number and thickness of varnish layers, while reflectance near/mid FT-IR spectroscopy provided valuable insights into their nature. The combined use of OCT and reflectance near/mid FT-IR in cleaning tests with different solvent mixtures clearly demonstrated the feasibility of selective removal of varnish layers. Finally, DHSPI- was used to determine whether the superficial and internal cracking phenomena were currently active and whether there were any significant weaknesses or instabilities within the wood supporting structure. In conclusion, the MOLAB research campaign has provided important information on the original artist painting technique, how best to approach the cleaning intervention and how to approach an intervention on the wooden support. We believe to have set a strong and reliable term of reference for future studies on this eminent artist.

5th CALL Project

Project Title: Ancient Andean Wooden Boards in the Museo delle Culture of Milan: A multi-Modal Analysis(AnBoMUDEC)

User Group Leader Samuele Tacconi (group leader)

Venue: Museo Delle Culture, Milan, Italy

This project focuses on two wooden boards in the collections of the Museo delle Culture (MUDEC) of Milan, pre-Hispanic Andean artifacts that belonged to a wider corpus of compartmentalized boards, with standardized features, often termed “yupanas” or “maquetas”. This project is part of the group leader’s PhD research that studies the chronology, morpho-typological classification, and cultural associations of these boards, which are one of the very few pre-Columbian Andean artifacts characterized by a prolonged and cross-cultural presence. However, despite their ubiquity and long-lasting significance to pre-Columbian South American peoples, they remain to this day one of the most poorly known artifacts in the archaeological record. Their cultural associations and typological classification are still unknown, and even their original function is subject to endless debate. The known examples of these boards are made of three different materials: stone, wood, and clay. Only a handful of the known examples proceed from controlled excavations, and we do not preserve information about the original context of most of them. Only a few known boards are made of wood and the two boards at MUDEC constitute some of the best-preserved examples. One of the group members, Dr Carolina Orsini – who has more than 2 decades of archaeological experience in Peru – is the senior curator of the collections of MUDEC, which include these two boards. The 3D documentation of these boards will be significant for conservation and preservation purposes. Along with the dendrochronological analysis, they will complement another IPERION Fixlab proposal made the same research group, which focuses on the radiocarbon dating of these two boards among others. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and biomolecular

analyses will shed light on wood degradation and bio-deterioration, and the possible presence of microorganisms.

The project includes morpho-typological studies of the outward features of these boards including their size, iconography, signs of wear and/or breakage, archival research, which will be carried out by the group leader to gather information about the provenance of the boards, and the collection of samples for radiocarbon dating. The goals of the analyses included in this proposal is to investigate in more detail the visual and physical properties of the boards, via 3D documentation, and their state of preservation, degradation and biodeterioration, for the purpose of the conservation of these boards and to gain a better understanding of their current physical conditions.

Finally, the C-14 dating will benefit from the dendro-chronological analysis. In more detail, the proposed analyses will comprise: 3D Documentation (MOLAB application for the use of the 3D structure-light scanner and 3D laser scanners) for the purpose of documenting and preserving the characteristics of these two objects, but also to better comprehend the physical characteristics of the wooden boards – e.g., to estimate the volume and density of the boards. These 3D models can enhance our understanding of the structure of these archaeological boards, and they can

aid in our investigation into the type of wood of which they are made, and the type of woodcarving. Finally, it can also shed light on possible signs of wear and damage that can point to the history, use and/or original function of these boards. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) depth-profiling/relaxometry (MOLAB application for the use of the NMR Machines). NMR profiling measurements will be conducted at different lateral positions of the two wooden boards starting from their backside aimed to gain deeper information about the homogeneity/inhomogeneity of the wood structure. The results potentially provide information about the presence of water and about structural changes, which can be related to the wood degradation. Learning more about the state of preservation of these two wooden boards is significant for their conservation as valuable pieces of cultural heritage of the pre-Columbian Andes. Biomolecular and biodeterioration analysis (MOLAB application for the use of Biomolecular Laboratory Equipment).

6th CALL Project

Project Title: Salvator Mundi: understanding interactions within Leonardo's circle (SALVATOR MUNDI)

User Group Leader Vincent Delieuvin (group leader)

Venue: ARCANES SARL, Paris, France

This interdisciplinary scientific project aimed to examine the creative context of one of Leonardo's most reproduced subjects: the Salvator Mundi. The ultimate goal is to understand one of the most recurring and replicated compositions of the High Renaissance in terms of workshop procedures, design processes and painting techniques by comparing several versions of the Salvator Mundi subject painted inside a closely related entourage. In this research project, we propose to examine

the painting using MOLAB's advanced methods, whose specific instrumental performance and expertise would provide the necessary complementary data to reveal further details about the painting technique, possible collaborations within Leonardo's workshop, as well as to better understand the chronology of Salvator Mundi's representations through comparison with the numerous variations of this subject. To this aim, a multidisciplinary team would benefit from the access to XRF mapping, hyper/multispectral VIS-NIR imaging, Optical coherence tomography (OCT), laser

microprofilometry and spot spectroscopy. The novelty of the proposed approach lies in focusing on a specific closed set of artworks attributed to members of Leonardo's workshop and proposing a group of machine learning tools that can maximize the extraction of relevant knowledge from this set of data. The analyses requested from MOLAB, hyperspectral camera in reflection/emission in VIS-NIR, multispectral VIS-NIR scanner (the previously reported - RIS), X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) in different modality – macro/micro mapping and confocal, Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), Optical Microprofilometry, FTIR, will be paramount for the integration and deepening of already available information. The complementarity of elemental and molecular imaging techniques, such as X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy (XRF) and Reflectance Imaging Spectroscopy (RIS) will provide comprehensive information relating to the artworks' chemical composition in image-wise modality.

Besides that, the so-generated images – especially by RIS in visible region - will be appropriately used for the spatial registration of other more site-specific analytical data – such as – OCT 3D, laser profilometric 3D data and spot FTIR and reflectance analyses. Being acquired with different spatial and spectral density, different algorithms are to be applied for their spatial registration and better fruition. Other aspects that were addressed are the overall evaluation of the conservation state, the possible presence and composition of overpainting and other evidence of

restoration interventions. In this respect, based on the outcomes of the overall imaging techniques, the selected regions of interest were examined with OCT, to obtain information on the presence, number, and thickness of superficial layers such as varnishes, as well as on inner layers, depending on their transparency to probing radiation. Such non-invasive stratigraphic examination is complementary to physical sampling performed previously as well as to confocal XRF measurements. Laser microprofilometry is used to provide quantitative information regarding the surface roughness, brush strokes, craquelures and other morphological features providing precious information.

6th CALL Project

Project Title: Evaluation of Coating Durability for Heritage Aircraft (CDHA)

User Group Leader Elodie Guilminot (group leader)

Venue: Arc Antique Laboratory, Nantes - FRANCE

This project is the continuation of our Transnational Access (TNA) accepted in the 3rd IPERION HS call that will be implemented in our laboratory in October 2022. In this access, we could evaluate the corrosion protection of six different treatments one week after their application over real aircraft wrecks. However, for analysing the lifetime efficiency and durability of these protection systems, it was necessary to study their surface condition and corrosion resistance after a prolonged exposure time, which was the objective of the proposal for the 6th IPERION HS call. Images in inset- C.Colonnier©, Arc'Antique - Grand Patrimoine de Loire Atlantique. A Supermarine Spitfire aircraft wing, the second, over the propeller blades of a P38 Lightning and the propeller from a DH Mosquito: Thus, we performed In-situ examinations by electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) and External reflection mid/near (FT-IR), to evaluate the corrosion protection durability and degradation of these protections nine months after their application. Although EIS is a widely used non-destructive technique for corrosion studies, its application in metallic heritage has been less widespread due to the need to perform in-situ

measurements on these objects. This is challenging because the objects are usually not completely flat, making it almost impossible to use traditional cells without affecting the surface condition. Recent research has focused on developing and implementing electrochemical cells that allow in-situ measurements of heritage pieces without affecting their conservation status. As a result, a gel polymer electrolyte cell (G-PE) has been developed, allowing in-situ EIS measurements on heritage objects with similar results to those offered by conventional liquid electrolyte cells. In addition, this technique can evaluate the complex system of metal, paint, corrosion product and protective

coatings, obtaining the anticorrosion effectiveness of the system. It is well known that the efficiency and durability of the protection treatments change according to the type of protection and the environment to which they are exposed. Besides, their stability is compromised by the substrate surface condition, and their protective power can be affected over time. This situation is critical in our study due to the particularity of the wreck's surfaces, going from an object with a slightly corroded metal surface, another with its original paint in a pretty

good condition, to one with a fragile and deteriorated surface. FT-IR complements EIS information by analysing the possible layer degradation after approximately nine months of their applications and exposition in uncontrollable outdoor/indoor conditions. The μ XRF results allowed us to visualize the distribution on the surface of chemical elements important for the corrosive processes such as Cu, Mn Fe and Si and furthermore of the main elements characterizing the corrosion patinas and

the surface impurities. A chromium-based paint was also identified for the black coating of the P-38 Lightning Propeller Blade. The other analysis techniques provided more information on the new layers of protection applied. Following cultural heritage needs and the requirements of conservation practices, all the coatings used in this project must be transparent or semi-transparent to visible light. Through the OCT techniques, we would measure the thickness of these different layers (projected to be thicker than 5 μm) by employing the 850 nm Fourier domain OCT equipment. In addition, the long-wavelength Fourier domain OCT equipment (wavelength of 1960 nm) with a larger penetration depth will be used for analyzing the corrosion products and the possible cracks/discontinuities formation after approximately one year of their applications. All the thicknesses of the layers could thus be determined except for the carboxylates (the layer was either non-existent or in too small a quantity to be detected). Only the FTIR technique was able to detect the local presence of carboxylates. FTIR is in fact a technique suitable for identifying the composition of coatings and their chemical changes after exposure. But after 9 months' exposure in an uncontrolled environment (hangartype), no significant degradation was measured by FTIR. As for the EIS analyses, they made it possible to establish the most effective protections depending on the surface condition of the object (corroded surface as for the Fécamps propeller; surface with paint residues as the wing of the Spitfire, or surface with its original paints like the blade of the P38). This analysis campaign also made it possible to consolidate our knowledge on the use of EIS in situ. these EIS-In situ measurements were thus able to be continued during the project.

6th CALL Project

Project Title: Non-Invasive Examination and Analysis of the Portrait of Philip the Good in the Musée des Beaux-Arts, Dijon: Insights into its Origin and Restoration History (MAP Philip the Good)

User Group Leader Jan Verheyen (group leader)

Venue: Musée des Beaux-Arts, Dijon, France

The Portrait of Philip the Good, kept at the Musée des Beaux-Arts in Dijon, France, presenting the Burgundian Duke Philip in a three-quarter profile, is traditionally assumed to be a copy of a presumed lost original dated around 1450 and tentatively attributed to the workshop of Rogier van der Weyden, like many other, similar versions of the same portrait. The interdependency and chronology of these portraits are at present poorly understood. The Dijon portrait could benefit largely from non-invasive imaging techniques, combined with the dendrochronological dating method and integrated into an in-depth art-historical analysis. Combining the pigment information, delivered by the MA-XRF-scans, the hyperspectral scans and the multispectral scans, with the dendrochronological dating performed by the Laboratoire d'Expertise du Bois et la Datation par Dendrochronologie, it should be possible to determine a trustworthy date of execution, which would narrow down the possible authors of the work. If the origin of the oak could be determined (Baltic or French are the most realistic possibilities), attribution would be facilitated. The portrait of Philip the Good preserved in the Musée des Beaux-Arts in Dijon is among numerous versions

dispersed across various European museums. It is suspected that several of these portraits, including the one in Dijon, are contemporaneous copies of the original portrait dating back to around 1445-1450. In a diagnostic campaign conducted by the Molab facilities in February 2024 at the museum, the panel underwent multispectral scanning, resulting in 32 reflectographies across 16 visible and 16 infrared wavelengths (395 – 2500 nm). At 1600 nm, a sharply defined underdrawing emerged in the facial area, while the hands exhibited considerable awkwardness and hesitation in the underdrawing, suggesting direct replication from an original, in the face but not the hands. Furthermore, MA-XRF scans elucidated the intricate recent restoration history of the dark blue background. The wooden panel was enlarged in the early twentieth century with supplemented wood, subsequently overpainted with modern pigments matching the original background colour but with a distinct chemical composition: cobalt-containing pigments Thénard's blue and Cerulean blue replaced the original copper-containing azurite. The limited palette of lead white, bone black, cinnabar, azurite and lead-tin yellow used in the original parts indicates a painting not postdating 1750. Particularly noteworthy is the construction of the gold colour in the Order of the Golden Fleece chain, with cinnabar overlaid with lead-tin yellow. Optical coherence tomography revealed subsequent application of glaze layers in this specific detail. The added modern oak wood obstructed potential dendrochronological dating. Without more precise dating, reliable attribution remains elusive; however, recent non-invasive imaging techniques have greatly clarified the panel's recent restoration history.

6th CALL Project

Project Title: The archaeological site of Kastri (ancient Pandosia) in Northwestern Greece (PANDOSIA)

User Group Leader Anthi Angeli (group leader)

Venue: The archaeological site of Kastri (ancient Pandosia) in Northwestern Greece

The PANDOSIA project was conducted at the archaeological site of Kastri (ancient Pandosia) in NW Greece, with aim to deepen our knowledge of the landscape and map the urban plan of the ancient city, allowing future archaeological excavation activities to be planned in a targeted manner. For the purposes of the project worked a team of the RES-DATA Lab of MOLAB.it (Italy) using LiDAR and Multispectral imagery and a team of the MOLAB.ro using thermal imaging technology to map and highlight surface and potential subsurface features and anomalies that might have archaeological importance. Aerial surveys were carried out using both active sensors (LiDAR) and passive sensors (high-resolution optical camera). The LiDAR survey at the Kastri archaeological site was carried out using a Riegl MiniVux-3 5-echo laser scanner, equipped with a GNSS PPK positioning system, used as a payload on a DJI Matrice 600 drone. The LiDAR acquisition covered a payload area of about 55 hectares. In order to conduct photogrammetric survey with a high-resolution optical camera, a flight was conducted over the Kastri site with the aim of being able to generate a very high resolution orthophoto of the entire site. A DJI Matrice 300 RTK drone with a 42-megapixel DJI P1 RGB camera was used. The results obtained show an articulated and complex situation of the hill, an effect of historical multi-

layering due to the long period of anthropogenic occupation of the site from the ancient period to the present. One of the main achievements during the project phase is certainly an extremely accurate and precise digital terrain model, from which it was possible to produce a mesh of regular isohypses, useful for understanding the morphology of the area. The pitch of the isohypses was set at meters 1 and 5. Analysis of the derived DTMs or DFMs revealed several features of archaeological interest, as well as multiple undistinguishable features that would suggest the presence of buried features, characterized mainly by microtopographic relief. From the derived data, the presence of collapse conoids, also identifiable from high-resolution orthophotos obtained by RGB camera, can also be discerned in the vicinity of terraces and masonry. The dataset, placed within the GIS platform (QGIS) allowed mapping, although not in their entirety, evidences related mainly to: (i) boundary walls, (ii) terracing system, (iii) vegetation-covered environments, (iv) probable quarry fronts, and (v) paths and access routes. It also showed some points considered interesting for the presence of microtopographies of possible anthropogenic nature, to be further investigated in future archaeological survey. In particular, LiDAR-based surveys have identified and mapped a complex

defensive structure on the hill with several walls that can be traced to at least three distinct construction phases.

Further equipment used in this project was a specialized unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), with three sensors (two cameras in visible spectrum and one in IR region), coupled with a multi-band RTK GNSS ground receiver with centimetre precision and other tools for precise micro-local weather assessment. Given the

characteristics of the site, there were two approaches: one for the area devoid of vegetation (site A – Hellenistic houses and Hellenistic fortification wall at the SE part of the site) and the other for the larger area (site B – the rest of the site, including the area within the Byzantine wall), covered by vegetation. For both situations a similar flight plan (nadiral images in a matrix configuration) was devised, but with different altitudes and image overlapping ratio. Thermal image sets were processed and corrected. Corrected data sets were further processed with a photogrammetric software resulting in several ortho-mosaics ready-to-use in GIS solutions. Complementary, the image sets coming from the visual spectrum cameras were also processed photogrammetrically, resulting in digital elevation models (DEM) and 3d mesh models. The results of the aerial thermal imaging surveys on site demonstrated the efficacy of thermal imaging technology applied in archaeological investigations. Measurements were performed at different times of day to highlight potential anomalies when the contrast of the different soil radiation emittances was at maximum (early morning and after sunset). In the Site A area, the survey showed the capability of the technology when used on bare ground, highlighting a possible subsurface structure within one of the houses. On site B area, with a vegetal cover, the method emphasized surface-level structures hidden in vegetation. Resulted thermal maps were georeferenced using ground positions recorded with GNSS and imported in a GIS system. The most impressive result was highlighted on the area corresponding to the Hellenistic construction. The lack of vegetation on this area allowed the thermal camera to receive a better signal from an anomaly – correlated in this case with a shallow buried fragment of structure. This type of result can be exploited furthermore by the archaeologists to study the site during the time period when the vegetation is completely removed or reduced and the soil is dry.

6th CALL Project

Project Title: Imperial Crown Analysis by Raman Spectroscopy (ICARE)
User Group Leader Martina Greisser (group leader)
Venue: Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna, Imperial Treasury, Austria

CARE was performed within the currently running 3-years research project CROWN (<https://www.projektreichskrone.at/>) at the Kunsthistorisches Museum (KHM), Vienna. CROWN aims to provide for the first time information on the materials, technology and state of preservation of the Imperial Crown, using an interdisciplinary perspective and state-of-the-art conservation and non-destructive scientific methods. The Imperial Crown was used for the coronations of the rulers of the Holy Roman Empire and – as one of the most iconic objects in European history – is kept in the Imperial Treasury (KHM) in Vienna today. The studies performed within a cooperation of art history/history, conservation, and the natural sciences leading scholars and scientists from Austria, Germany, France and Northern Italy will establish a new basis for the scholarly discussion of the crown's controversial dating (960 – 1150 CE) and provenance [1, 2] and its state of preservation by providing HIROX 3-D microscopic images, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), fibre optic reflectance (FORS) and Raman spectroscopic data. The comprehensive scientific studies focus on the characterisation of the decorative elements – multi-coloured enamels, gemstones, and pearls. Main objectives concern the detailed investigation of the cloisonné work, its manufacturing process and the enamels' chemical composition. Enamel being the most sensitive material present, the determination of degradation and corrosion observed on the different enamel colours is of major importance for the crown's future preservation. The IPERION-HS facilities were chosen as no suitable mobile Raman system and experienced researchers for studying enamel on Cultural Heritage objects with this analytical technique are available in Austria. The enamels cover translucent as well as opaque, white, flesh tone, yellow, red, green, blue, brown and black varieties. Altogether around 140 spectra were collected using MOLAB's MOVIDA software. In a first step, the raw data were evaluated confirming most of the assumptions based on the XRF and FORS results. As a matrix mainly alkali glass could be detected, opaque enamels generally contain calcium antimonate as an opacifier, the yellow enamels are based on modified Naples yellow. For turquoise, green and blue enamels iron oxide bands could be detected for colouring agents. As expected, the cobalt present as the main colouring element in the deeper blue varieties (cobalt glasses) could not be detected by Raman. The brown enamels seem to be iron and manganese oxide based, no definite conclusion could be obtained for the compositions of the red and black enamels as well as corrosion products.

Table 4 - Summary of executed projects M28-48

Access granted by each MOLAB facility (N. Days ON-SITE + TRAVEL)		Project ID/Acronym/Title/USERS's leader	Discipline + Objectives	Short description of work
<p>RP2 reported</p> <p>MOLAB.fr1 (CNRS) 3 days</p> <p>MOLAB.de1 (SPK/RWTH) 6 days <u>INCORRECT</u></p> <p>MOLAB.gr3 (Of-ADC) 0 days (2ndRP) <u>INCORRECT</u></p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_c 4 days</p>	<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.fr1 (CNRS) 7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.de1 (SPK/RWTH) 2 days</p> <p>MOLAB.gr 3 (Of-ADC) 5 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_c 4 days In-kind</p>	<p>Mol_1 DIACOMM: Diagnostics for Conservation at Müstair Monastery</p> <p>Patrick Cassitti, Foundation Pro Monastery of St. John, Müstair, Switzerland</p>	<p>Humanities; material sciences</p> <p>To address the lack of understanding of the wall painting constituents (original and not) with a multitechnical approach to support the long-term preservation of the paintings.</p>	<p>This wide MOLAB mission commenced in the last report with access provided by MOLAB.gr (IESL) and MOLAB fr (LRMH). The study focused on a limited but representative part of the painted surface: the northern wall in front of the gallery (approx. 10 m²). Remote sensing techniques LIBS/LIF/Raman, Remote LIBS, Remote Raman/LIF, XRD/XRF were provided by MOLAB.uk; MOLAB.fr and MOLAB.it. Nuclear magnetic resonance NMR by MOLAB.de; Both Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DHSPI) and Acoustic Tomography. The project worked to identify areas with different acoustic/thermal/magnetic behaviour to identify those corresponding to detachment or loss of cohesion. The mapping technique was used to define the measurement spots for the point analysis. The individuation of hollow/less cohesive areas will be of importance, showing the conservation conditions of the medieval cycle, provides a starting point for planning any intervention campaign.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.fr1 7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.cy1 6 days</p>	<p>Mol_3 PYRITEDINOSAUR: OCT, 3D structure -light scanner and integrated XRD-XRF applied to conservation dinosaurs fossils with pyrite decay and evaluation of innovate method conservation</p> <p>Nuria Miguel, Aragonese School of Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage (ESCYRA)</p>	<p>Chemistry; Material sciences; Earth Sciences and Environment</p> <p>A comprehensive study on the pyrite degradation of the Ariño Fossils in different environmental conditions by evaluating commercial</p>	<p>Integrated XRD-XRF and LIBS from MOLAB.fr was used to determine the different phases (chemical composition and crystal structure) and the description of the microstructure (grain size, texture) of the pyritized fossils. - 3D structure-light scanner (SLS) and Photogrammetric technique (PH) from MOLAB.cy to monitor structural changes</p>	

		consolidants and new methodologies for long term efficiency	based on environmental and climatic change.
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_a 5 days</p> <p>MOLAB.pl1 NCU 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB.es 1 5 days</p> <p>MOLAB.uk1 8 days</p>	<p>Mol_22 EPHA: Evaluation of Protection for Heritage Aircraft</p> <p>Elodie Guilminot ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine, Nanates, France</p>	<p>Material science</p> <p>Evaluation of a protective coating on three different real aircrafts wrecks</p>	<p>Through analyses of In-situ electrochemical Examinations (MOLAB.es), Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) (MOLAB.pl), Micro X-ray Fluorescence (μXRF), and External reflection mid/near-FT-IR (MOLAB.it) to evaluate the corrosion protection, thickness and durability of the coating.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_a 8 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it1 CNR-SCITEC 7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it2 UNIPG 7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.uk1 7 days</p>	<p>Mol_24 HFTV-ReVIS: The Hunt Frieze of Tomb II at Vergina, Greece: A Novel Interdisciplinary Approach for the Scientific Investigation and Revisualization of a Painted Masterpiece of the Classical World)</p> <p>Hariclia Brecoulaki National Hellenic Research Foundation, Greece</p>	<p>Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics</p> <p>The scientific objectives of HFTV-ReVis project were a) to get information on the exact composition of the colours (pigments and binders), the texture and depth of the paint layers and b) to bring to light specific iconographic elements from the hunt frieze which nowadays are not perceivable due to the poor state of the pictorial surface</p>	<p>The two phases of the campaign included the in-situ implementation of different photographic methods and spectroscopic non-invasive analytical techniques providing complementary elemental, molecular and crystalline phase characterization of the hunt frieze's colour palette, along with the evaluation and interpretation of the findings.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.gr2 FORTH-IMS 9 days</p>	<p>Mol_17 SuBaiae: Integrating on-land and shallow marine geophysical investigations to detect buried archeological features in a coastal area. The Roman site of Baiae, Phlegrean Fields Archaeological Park (Naples, Italy (SuBaiae)</p> <p>Fabio Pagano Phlegrean Fields Archaeological Park, Naples, Italy</p>	<p>Earth sciences and environment, engineering and technology, humanities, Information and communication technologies</p> <p>The project combines land-based and ultra-shallow marine geophysical methods to investigate and reconstruct the</p>	<p>The present geophysical investigations were aimed to fill the gap of data in the very shallow water and onshore environments of the submerged site of Baiae. The surveys conducted by MOLAB.gr (IMS) include: 1) dynamic and static 3-D Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) to examine the sedimentary layers below the seabed and 2) Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) to</p>

		onshore-offshore hidden built environment in a selected coastal area of the Roman site of Baiae (Naples, Italy)	check the continuation of remains on the coast
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_a 7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it1 CNR-SCITEC 5 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it2 UNIPG 5 days</p>	<p>Mol_29 MoMNoPSAF: The materiality of the Medieval North – the palette of Swedish and Finnish reconstructed Manuscripts</p> <p>Thea Winther Swedish National Archives, Sweden</p>	<p>Chemistry, humanities, material science</p> <p>The Latin book culture of medieval Sweden (containing present-day Finland) remains poorly known due to the challenges of the source material. By applying scientific methods, data that further enables us to understand the manufacture, origin, and qualities of these fragments have been collected</p>	<p>10 fragments were examined by MOLAB.it CNR (SCITEC, UNIPG, ISPC_a) collecting macro-XRF and HSI. 136 FTIR spectra, 23 Raman spectra, 93 UV-VIS reflectance and 13 UV-VIS Fluorescence spectra. μ-XRF mapping were conducted for eight details. The results of this study of these medieval Swedish manuscript pages has shown a complexity and a well-developed craftsmanship that reflect the developing book culture of high- and late-medieval Sweden.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.it3 CNR-INO 6 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it1 CNR-SCITEC 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB.uk1 NTU 11 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_a 4 days (in-kind)</p> <p>MOLAB.pl1 NCU 7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.gr3 Of-ADC 5 days</p>	<p>Mol_47 Synthetic varnishes Can deteriorated synthetic varnishes be removed from sensitive modern paint films such as acrylic emulsions and polyvinyl acetates using novel cleaning methods?</p> <p>Laura Homer National Museum of Art, Norway</p>	<p>Chemistry, humanities, material science</p> <p>Aims were to conduct a non-invasive, multimodal analytical study of ten acrylic and polyvinyl acetate (PVAc) paintings represented in the museum collection to investigate the removability of commercial artists' varnishes</p>	<p>All instruments were employed for measurements of all 10 case study paintings- MOLAB.it came with single-point external reflection mid-IR spectroscopy. MOLAB.uk came with hybrid optical coherence tomography at 1300 nm with co-aligned spectral imaging and remote shortwave infrared hyperspectral imaging (SWIR-HSI; 1000–2500 nm). MOLAB.it also came with optical micro-profilometry. MOLAB.pl with optical coherence tomography at 850 nm. MOLAB.gr came with ultrasonic acoustic tomography.</p>

<p>MOLAB.fr1 LRMF 5 days</p> <p>MOLAB.gr1 IESL 7 days</p>	<p>Mol_41 Giotto@Bardi Advanced diagnostic procedures for the informed restoration intervention on fresco wall paintings by Giotto, Bardi Chapel (Basilica Santa Croce, Florence, Italy)</p> <p>Antonina Chaban CNR, National Institute of Optics, Italy</p>	<p>Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics</p> <p>This project aimed at optimizing the methodology to address issues of conservation state of the fresco wall paintings in the Bardi Chapel, by integrating the state-of-art non-invasive structural and physical-chemical characterization tools, suitable for the purpose.</p>	<p>The DHSPI-SIRT complementary approach (MOLAB.gr and MOLAB.fr respectively) allowed a holistic assessment of thermodynamic behaviour of the subsurface multi-layered fresco wall painting system in its complexity. Going into detail, the THz Imaging and Spectroscopy method made a significant contribution to this project through non-invasive subsurface stratigraphic analysis on the smaller areas, identified through the initial full-field characterization by DHSPI and SIRT. The THz Imaging and Spectroscopy technique was used to detect discontinuities and to assess their in-depth location and dimensions, as well as to differentiate between pigments on the wall painting surface.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.es1 CSIC 5 days</p>	<p>Mol_49 SIM Saving Industrial Metals</p> <p>David Thickett English Heritage</p>	<p>Chemistry, Earth Science and environment</p> <p>The main objectives were to examine the five most widely used coatings were applied to steel dyes in 2010 and some of the machinery in 2018. These naturally aged coatings, in a well characterised environment, provide an ideal opportunity to assess their long term effectiveness.</p>	<p>Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy, EIS provided by MOLAB.es was used for assessing coating efficacy by generating significant data rapidly. The move towards gel-based electrolytes has allowed its use on complex surfaces. This resulted particularly useful for vertical surfaces which are known to be problematic for even coating application. The machinery mainly has vertical surfaces. The gel also allows analysis with minimal disruption or interference to the coating, allowing further analyses. The reversibility of the coatings will be assessed after the project.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.gr1 IESL 5 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_a</p>	<p>MOL_53 CALPIA Rediscovery of Callisto Piazza master's art. A unique research opportunity during the restoration of the "Assumption and Coronation of the Virgin"</p>	<p>Humanities, physics</p> <p>This project aims to characterize Piazza's original painting technique by means of a broad in-depth scientific</p>	<p>Vis-NIR hyperspectral imaging (MOLAB.it) helped to make an initial identification of surface pigments through end-member extraction. The combined use of OCT (MOLAB.pl) and reflectance near/mid FT-IR (MOLAB.it) in cleaning tests with different</p>

<p>7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it1 CNR-SCITEC 6 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it3 CNR-INO 6 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it2 UNIPG 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB.pl1 6 days</p>	<p>panel painting in Lugano (CH)</p> <p>Corinna Ludovica, Koch Dandolo Lugano Municipality- Culture section</p>	<p>examination and to clarify the overpainting and varnish stratification found on the painting as well as to correctly address the cleaning intervention, by means of surface and depth profiling mapping techniques</p>	<p>solvent mixtures clearly demonstrated the feasibility of selective removal of varnish layers. Finally, DHSPI-(MOLAB.gr) was used to determine whether the superficial and internal cracking phenomena were currently active and whether there were any significant weaknesses or instabilities within the wood supporting structure.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.de1 SPK/RWTH 7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.cy1 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB.pt1 5 days</p>	<p>Mol_31 AnBoMUDEC Ancient Andean Wooden Boards in the Museo delle Culture of Milan: A multi-Modal Analysis</p> <p>Samuele Tacconi University of East Anglia, UK</p>	<p>Humanities, social sciences</p> <p>The goals of the analyses included in this proposal is to investigate the state of preservation, degradation and biodeterioration, for the purpose of the conservation of these boards and to gain a better understanding of their current physical conditions</p>	<p>3D Documentation was utilized (MOLAB.cy) for the purpose of documenting and preserving the characteristics of these two objects, but also to better comprehend the physical characteristics of the wooden boards – e.g., to estimate the volume and density of the boards. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) depth-profiling/relaxometry (MOLAB.de) measurements conducted at different lateral positions of the two wooden boards starting from their backside aimed to gain deeper information about the homogeneity/inhomogeneity of the wood structure. Learning more about the state of preservation of these two wooden boards is significant for their conservation as valuable pieces of cultural heritage of the pre-Columbian Andes for which Biomolecular and biodeterioration analysis (MOLAB.pt) could be conducted.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.it1 CNR-SCITEC 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it2 UNIPG 4 days</p>	<p>Mol_62 Salvator Mundi understanding interactions within Leonardo's circle</p> <p>Vincent Delieuvin Louvre Museum, Paris, France</p>	<p>Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology</p> <p>The ultimate goal of the Salvator Mundi project is to understand one of</p>	<p>The analyses requested from MOLAB.it (CNR-SCITEC, UNIPG, CNR-INO) and MOLAB.pl included hyperspectral camera in reflection/emission in VIS-NIR, multispectral VIS-NIR scanner (the previously reported - RIS), X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) in different modality – macro/micro mapping and</p>

<p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_a 7 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it3 CNR-INO 6 days</p> <p>MOLAB.pl1 NCU 6 days</p>		<p>the most recurring and replicated compositions of the High Renaissance in terms of workshop procedures, design processes and painting techniques by comparing several versions of the Salvator Mundi subject painted inside a closely related entourage.</p>	<p>confocal, Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), Optical Microprofilometry and FTIR are paramount for the integration and deepening of already available information. The complementarity of elemental and molecular imaging techniques, such as X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy (XRF) and Reflectance Imaging Spectroscopy (RIS) provide comprehensive information relating to the artworks' chemical composition in image-wise modality.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_a 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB.es1 CSIC 5 days</p>	<p>Mol_57 CDHA Evaluation of Coating Durability for Heritage Aircraft</p> <p>Elodie Guilminot Arc Antique Laboratory, Nantes - FRANCE</p>	<p>Material science</p> <p>To perform In-situ electrochemical examinations by electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) and External reflection mid/near (FT-IR), to evaluate the corrosion protection durability and degradation of the protection on aircraft wrecks nine months after their application. This project is a continuation of the EPHA project.</p>	<p>The in-situ EIS measurements provided by MOLAB.es on aircraft wreckage pieces to evaluate the complex system of metal, paint, corrosion product and protective coatings, obtaining the anticorrosion effectiveness of the system. It is well known that the efficiency and durability of the protection treatments change according to the type of protection and the environment to which they are exposed. Complementary examinations were carried out by vibrational spectroscopic methods, namely external reflection FTIR by MOLAB.it for analysing the lifetime efficiency and durability of these protection systems, by studying their surface condition and corrosion resistance after a prolonged exposure time</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.it1 CNR-SCITEC 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_a 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it3</p>	<p>Mol_68 Map Philip the Good Non-Invasive Examination and Analysis of the Portrait of Philip the Good in the Musée des Beaux-Arts, Dijon: Insights into its Origin and Restoration History</p> <p>Jan Verheyen Catholic University of Leuven</p>	<p>Humanities, physics</p> <p>The Dijon portrait could benefit largely from non-invasive imaging techniques, combined with the dendrochronological dating method and integrated into an in-depth art-historical analysis.</p>	<p>In a diagnostic campaign conducted by the Molab facilities (MOLAB.it CNR-SCITEC, INO and MOLAB.pl) at the museum, the panel underwent multispectral scanning, resulting in 32 reflectographies across 16 visible and 16 infrared wavelengths (395 – 2500 nm). At 1600 nm, a sharply defined underdrawing emerged in the facial area, while the hands</p>

<p>CNR-INO 6 days</p> <p>MOLAB.pl1 NCU 6 days</p>		<p>Clarification of restoration history</p>	<p>exhibited considerable awkwardness and hesitation in the underdrawing, suggesting direct replication from an original, in the face but not the hands. Furthermore, MA-XRF scans elucidated the intricate recent restoration history of the dark blue background.</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.it5 CNR-ISPC 7 days In-kind</p> <p>MOLAB.ro1 INOE 11 days</p>	<p>MoI_58 PANDOSIA The archaeological site of Kastri (ancient Pandosia) in Northwestern Greece</p> <p>Anthi Angeli Ephorate of Antiquities of Preveza, Greece</p>	<p>Humanities</p> <p>The PANDOSIA projects aim to deepen the knowledge of the landscape and map the urban plan of the ancient city, allowing future archaeological excavation activities to be planned in a targeted manner at the archaeological site of Kastri (ancient Pandosia) in NW Greece</p>	<p>The team from MOLAB.it using LiDAR and Multispectral imagery and a team of the MOLAB.ro using thermal imaging technology were utilized to map and highlight surface and potential subsurface features and anomalies that might have archaeological importance. Aerial surveys were carried out using both active sensors (LiDAR) and passive sensors (high-resolution optical camera). The survey showed the capability of the technology when used on bare ground, highlighting a possible subsurface structure within one of the houses. Another site, with a vegetal cover, the method emphasized surface-level structures hidden in vegetation. Resulted thermal maps were georeferenced using ground positions recorded with GNSS and imported in a GIS system. The most impressive result was highlighted on the area corresponding to the Hellenistic construction</p>
<p>RP3</p> <p>MOLAB.it1 CNR-SCITEC 4 days</p> <p>MOLAB.it4 CNR-ISPC_a 4 days (in-kind)</p>	<p>MOL_56 ICARE Imperial Crown Analysis by Raman Spectroscopy</p> <p>Martina Greisser Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna, Austria</p>	<p>Chemistry, humanities, material science</p> <p>Main objectives concern the detailed investigation of the cloisonné work, its manufacturing process and the enamels' chemical composition. Enamel being the most sensitive material present, the</p>	<p>Raman measurements were conducted by MOLAB.it where the matrix highlighted mainly alkali glass, the opaque enamels were observed to contain calcium antimonate as an opacifier and the yellow enamels are based on modified Naples yellow. For turquoise, green and blue enamels iron oxide bands could be detected for colouring agents. As expected, the cobalt present as the main colouring element in the deeper blue varieties (cobalt</p>

		<p>determination of degradation and corrosion observed on the different enamel colours is of major importance for the crown's future preservation.</p>	<p>glasses) could not be detected by Raman. The brown enamels seem to be iron and manganese oxide based, no definite conclusion could be obtained for the compositions of the red and black enamels. The presence of corrosion products was noted.</p>
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3. CONCLUSIONS

The MOLAB programme in the period M28-M48 concentrated its activities in providing a quality access service considering that access began only in M18 due to the delay caused by Covid-19. This meant that much effort had to be spent by MOLAB coordination to ensure a smooth as possible running operation with all involved providers for the MOLAB Users, as well as to include the proposals granted in the final calls for access (fifth and sixth calls).

It can be accurately reported that due to the extra six months extension, MOLAB was successful in reaching its access goals by month 48. **MOLAB in IPERION HS promised to provide 67 access campaigns**, (D4.1 accounts for 17). Herein, MOLAB providers account for a further 55 access campaigns to 16 projects. **MOLAB in IPERION HS has been able to provide 72 access campaigns, actually 107,5% of total promised MOLAB TNA expected to be carried out in terms of research projects.**

It remains to be mentioned that the demand for MOLAB services remained very high, on average 2.5 times more than the actual slots available in the IPERION HS project.

To this end, MOLAB has and will continue to deliver relevant scientific achievements and technical goals.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX I. MOLAB Proposals received and evaluated (Calls 5-6)

WP4- MOLAB					
PROPOSALS RECEIVED AND EVALUATED DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD					
User Group Member			Project		Access Provider
Name	Home Institution, Country	n. Users per facility (total)	ID/Acronym/Title	Selected Y/N	Short name
5th Call					
Samuele Tacconi	University of East Anglia, UK	3 (9)	Mol_11 AmBoMKB: Ancient Andean Stone Board in the Museum der Kulturen of Basel: A Multi-Modal Study	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC) MOLAB.cy MOLAB.fr
Samuele Tacconi	University of East Anglia, UK	5 (15)	Mol_31 AnBoMUDEC: Ancient Andean Wooden Boards in the Museo delle Culture of Milan: A Multi-Modal Analysis	Y	MOLAB.de MOLAB.cy MOLAB.pt
Wissam Khalil	Lebanese University, LB	5 (5)	Mol_35 SMS: In Search of the Mithraeum of Sidon	N	MOLAB.gr (IMS)
Jan Verheyen	Catholic University of Leuven (KU Leuven), BE	3 (15)	Mol_46 Map Philip the Good: A Multi-disciplinary Analysis of the Portrait of Philip the Good	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/UNIPG/INO/ISPC _a) MOLAB.pl
Martina Greisser	Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna, Austria	7 (14)	Mol_50 ICARE: Imperial Crown Analysis by Raman Spectroscopy	N	MOLAB.it (CNR-SCITEC) MOLAB.pl
Malin Borin	Gothenburg Museum of Art, Sweden	7 (42)	Mol_51 REMBRANDT WORKSHOP: Rembrandt, Workshop or Follower? An Investigation into Material and technique of the Adoration of the Magi in the Collection of the Gothenburg Museum Of Art	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/UNIPG/INO/ISPC _a) MOLAB.pl MOLAB.fr
Helen Howards	National Gallery, London, UK	6 (36)	MOL_52 MAMAT: Margarito d'Arezzo: a study of his painting materials and techniques	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/UNIPG/INO/ISPC _a) MOLAB.pl MOLAB.fr
Corinna Ludovica, Koch Dandolo	Lugano Municipality Culture section, Switzerland	4 (28)	Mol_53 CALPIA: Rediscovery of Callisto Piazza master's art. A unique research opportunity during the restoration of the "Assumption and Coronation of the Virgin" panel painting in Lugano (CH)	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/UNIPG/INO/ISPC _a) MOLAB.pl MOLAB.fr MOLAB.gr (FORTH-IESL)
Elodie Guilminot	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine, FR	18 (72)	Mol_54 CDHA: Evaluation of Coating Durability for Heritage Aircraft	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC) MOLAB.pl MOLAB.uk MOLAB.es
Joan Abela	Notarial Archives Foundation, Malta	5 (15)	Mol_55 LLPM: Locked Letters Project – Malta	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/INO) MOLAB.fr
6th Call					
Martina Greisser	Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna, Austria	7 (7)	Mol_56 ICARE: Imperial Crown Analysis by Raman Spectroscopy	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR-SCITEC)
Elodie Guilminot	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine, FR	18 (72)	Mol_57 CDHA: Evaluation of Coating Durability for Heritage Aircraft	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC) MOLAB.pl MOLAB.uk MOLAB.es

Anthi Angeli	Ephorate of Antiquities of Preveza, Greece	2 (4)	Mol_58 PANDOSIA: Landscape archaeology in Kastrì-Pandosia on the Acheron river	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR_ISPC _c) MOLAB.ro
Stanislav Stanev	Ancient Plovdiv Municipal Institute, BG	2 (2)	Mol_60 AIMFEBP: Aerial investigation of the mosaic floors of the Episcopal (Bishop's) Basilica of Philippopolis (Plovdiv, Bulgaria)	N	MOLAB.ro
Maria Luisa Vázquez de Ágreos Pascua	Universitat de València, ES	1 (1)	Mol_61 ArtBio_SanNicolas: Science for the Arts and Heritage Conservation: Biomolecular and Bioanalytical Techniques applied to the artistic collection of the Church-Museum of San Nicolás de València	N	MOLAB.pt
Vincent Delieuvin	Louvre Museum, France	10 (50)	Mol_62 SALVATOR MUNDI: Salvator Mundi: understanding interactions within Leonardo's circle	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/UNIPG/INO/ISPC _a) MOLAB.pl
Nikolay Nenov	Rousse Regional Museum of History, Bulgaria	1 (1)	Mol_63 APIRHCI: Aerial photogrammetry investigation of the rock-hewn churches of Ivanovo	N	MOLAB.ro
Hamada Kotb	The University of Bologna-Fayoum University	3 (3)	Mol_64 ZAAFRAN: Non-destructive techniques applied to Zaafran Palace, Egypt.	N	MOLAB.ro
Jan Verheyen	Catholic University of Leuven (KU Leuven), BE	2 (6)	Mol_46 Map Philip the Good: A Multi-disciplinary Analysis of the Portrait of Philip the Good	Y	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/INO) MOLAB.pl
Miguel Angel Respaldiza Galisteo	Universidad De Sevilla	11 (44)	Mol_66 MURICHAR: Characterization of Murillo's paintings and related anonymous copies from the collections of the Archdiocese of Seville	N	MOLAB.it (CNR_SCITEC/UNIPG/ISPC _a) MOLAB.pl

APPENDIX II. Selected Projects at MOLAB PRP Meetings (Calls 5-6)

N°	ID Project Acronym	Genre	Project Title	User Group Leader	Gender	Affiliation	Country
<i>Selected at 5th M-PRP Meeting</i>							
1	Mol_31 AnBoMUDEC	Wood	Ancient Andean Wooden Boards in the Museo delle Culture of Milan: A multi-modal Analysis	S. Tacconi	M	University of East Anglia	UK
2	Mol_53 CALPIA	Paintings	Rediscovery of Callisto Piazza master's art. A unique research opportunity during the restoration of the "Assumption and Coronation of the Virgin" panel painting in Lugano (CH)	C. L. Koch Dandolo	F	Lugano Municipality- Culture section	CH
<i>Selected at 6th M-PRP Meeting</i>							
1	Mol_62 SALVATOR MUNDI	Paintings	understanding interactions within Leonardo's circle	V. Delieuvin	M	Louvre Museum	FR
2	Mol_57 CDHA	Aircraft	Evaluation of Coating Durability for Heritage Aircraft	E. Guilminot	F	Arc Antique Laboratory, Nantes	FR
3	Mol_68 Map Philip the Good	Paintings	Non-Invasive Examination and Analysis of the Portrait of Philip the Good in the Musée des Beaux-Arts, Dijon: Insights into its Origin and Restoration History	J. Verheyen	F	Catholic University of Leuven	BE
4	Mol_58 Pandosia	Archaeological site	The archaeological site of Kastri (ancient Pandosia) in Northwestern Greece	A. Angeli	F	Ephorate of Antiquities of Preveza, Greece	GR
5	Mol_56 ICARE	Crown	Imperial Crown Analysis by Raman Spectroscopy	M. Greisser	F	Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna	AT

APPENDIX III. MOLAB Users for projects carried out (Calls 1-6)

RESEARCHER				EMPLOYING ORGANIZATION/ HOME INSTITUTION			OTHER INFORMATION	
First Name	Last Name	Gender	Nationality	Name	Country	Legal status ¹	User project acronym	Activity domain ²
Nuria	Miguel	Female	Spain	Aragonese School of Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage (ESCYRA)	Spain	UNI	PYRITEDINOSAUR	Chemistry, Earth sciences and Environment, Material science
Luis	Alcalá	Male	Spain	Palaeontological Network Foundation of Teruel-Dinópolis (FCPTD)-Dinópolis	Spain	RES	PYRITEDINOSAUR	Chemistry, Earth sciences and Environment, Material science
Ana	González	Female	Spain	Palaeontological Network Foundation of Teruel-Dinópolis (FCPTD)-Dinópolis	Spain	RES	PYRITEDINOSAUR	Chemistry, Earth sciences and Environment, Material science
Luis	Mampel	Male	Spain	Palaeontological Network Foundation of Teruel-Dinópolis (FCPTD)-Dinópolis	Spain	RES	PYRITEDINOSAUR	Chemistry, Earth sciences and Environment, Material science
Eduardo	Espílez	Male	Spain	Aragon Materials Science Institute (INMA)	Spain	UNI	PYRITEDINOSAUR	Chemistry, Earth sciences and Environment, Material science
Scott	Mitchell	Male	GB	Aragon Materials Science Institute (INMA)	Spain	UNI	PYRITEDINOSAUR	Chemistry, Earth sciences and Environment, Material science
Guillermo	Torres	Male	Spain	Aragon Materials Science Institute (INMA)	Spain	UNI	PYRITEDINOSAUR	Chemistry, Earth sciences and Environment, Material science
Carmen	De Peña	Female	Spain	Aragon Materials Science Institute (INMA)	Spain	UNI	PYRITEDINOSAUR	Chemistry, Earth sciences and Environment, Material science
Andrés	Seral	Male	Spain	Aragon Materials Science Institute (INMA)	Spain	UNI	PYRITEDINOSAUR	Chemistry, Earth sciences and Environment, Material science
Fabio	Pagano	Male	Italy	Ministry of Cultural Heritage and Activities and Tourism (MIBACT)	Italy	OTH	SuBaiae	Earth sciences and Environment, Engineering and Technology, Humanities, Information and Communication technologies
Crescenzo	Violante	Male	Italy	National Research Council- CNR Institute of Heritage Science (ISPC)	Italy	RES	SuBaiae	Earth sciences and Environment, Engineering and Technology, Humanities, Information and Communication technologies
Enrico	Gallocchio	Male	Italy	Ministry of Culture (MIC)	Italy	OTH	SuBaiae	Earth sciences and Environment, Engineering and Technology, Humanities,

								Information and Communication technologies
Marida	Salvatori	Female	Italy	Ministry of Culture (MIC)	Italy	OTH	SuBaiae	Earth sciences and Environment, Engineering and Technology, Humanities, Information and Communication technologies
Augusto	Palombini	Male	Italy	National Research Council- CNR Institute of Heritage Science (ISPC)	Italy	RES	SuBaiae	Earth sciences and Environment, Engineering and Technology, Humanities, Information and Communication technologies
Patrick	Cassitti	Male	Italy	Foundation Pro Monastery of St. John	Switzerland	PRV	DIACOMM	Humanities, Material sciences
Francesca	Piqué	Female	Italy	Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana	Switzerland	UNI	DIACOMM	Humanities, Material sciences
Patrizia	Moretti	Female	Italy	Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana	Switzerland	UNI	DIACOMM	Humanities, Material sciences
Elodie	Guilminot	Female	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Cesar	Escobar Claros	Male	Colombia	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Jane	Echinard	Female	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Gilles	Baron	Male	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Stéphane	Lemoine	Male	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Charlene	Pelé-Meziani	Female	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Loretta	Rosseti	Female	Italy	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Sylvie	Labroche	Female	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Aymeric	Raimon	Male	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Magali	Brunet	Female	France	Centre d'élaboration de matériaux et d'études structurales - CEMES-CNRS	France	RES	EPHA	Material science
Luc	Robbiola	Male	France	Laboratoire TRACES	France	RES	EPHA	Material science

Andrea	Balbo	Male	Italy	University of Ferrara (Department of Engineering)	Italy	UNI	EPHA	Material science
Cecilia	Monticelli	Female	Italy	University of Ferrara (Department of Engineering)	Italy	UNI	EPHA	Material science
Cristina	Chiavari	Female	Italy	University of Bologna (Department of Cultural Heritage)	Italy	UNI	EPHA	Material science
Carla	Martini	Female	Italy	University of Bologna (Department of Industrial Chemistry "Toso Montanari")	Italy	UNI	EPHA	Material science
Elena	Bernardi	Female	Italy	University of Bologna (Department of Industrial Chemistry "Toso Montanari")	Italy	UNI	EPHA	Material science
Cecilia	Velino	Female	Italy	University of Bologna (Department of Industrial Chemistry "Toso Montanari")	Italy	UNI	EPHA	Material science
Jaromir	Fišer	Male	Czech	Czech technical university in Prague (Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering)	Czech	UNI	EPHA	Material science
Michaela	Florescu	Female	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	OTH	EPHA	Material science
Hariclia	Brecoulak	Female	Greece	National Hellenic Research Foundation	Greece	RES	HFTV-ReVIS	Chemistry, Humanities, Material science, Physics
Andreas	Karydas	Male	Greece	Institute of Nuclear and Particle Physics, NCSR Demokritos	Greece	UNI	HFTV-ReVIS	Chemistry, Humanities, Material science, Physics
Kalliopi	Tsampa	Female	Greece	Institute of Nuclear and Particle Physics, NCSR Demokritos	Greece	UNI	HFTV-ReVIS	Chemistry, Humanities, Material science, Physics
Giovanni	Verri	Male	Italy	Art Institute of Chicago	USA	RES	HFTV-ReVIS	Chemistry, Humanities, Material science, Physics
Corinna Ludovica	Koch Dandolo	Female	Swiss	Lugano Municipality - culture section	Switzerland	OTH	CALPIA	Humanities Physics
Endrio	Ruggiero	Male	Swiss	Ufficio dei beni culturali, Bellinzona	Switzerland	RES	CALPIA	Humanities Physics

Laura	Calderari	Female	Swiss	Ufficio dei beni culturali, Bellinzona	Switzerland	RES	CALPIA	Humanities Physics
Helena	Bernal	Female	Swiss	Ufficio dei beni culturali, Bellinzona	Switzerland	RES	CALPIA	Humanities Physics
Samuele	Tacconi	Male	Italy	University of East Anglia, Norwich	UK	UNI	AnBoMUDEC	Humanities Social sciences
George Fu-Yan	Lau	Male	USA	University of East Anglia, Norwich	UK	UNI	AnBoMUDEC	Humanities Social sciences
Carolina	Orsini	Female	Italy	Mudec-Museo delle Culture, Milan	Italy	RES	AnBoMUDEC	Humanities Social sciences
Vincent	Delieuvin	Male	France	Louvre Museum	France	OTH	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Cinzia	Pasquale	Female	Italy	Arcanes SARL	France	PRV	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Jan	Blažek	Female	Czechia	Institute of Information Theory and Automation, Czech Academy of Sciences	Czech Republic	RES	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Barbara	Zitová	Female	Czechia	Institute of Information Theory and Automation, Czech Academy of Sciences	Czech Republic	RES	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Diane	Marchioni	Female	France	RES SARL	France	PRV	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Ashley	Vidler	Male	Italy	RES SARL	France	PRV	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Viviane	Leichlé	Female	France	RES SARL	France	PRV	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Leslie	Weber-Robardet	Female	France	RES SARL	France	PRV	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Olivier	Bobin	Male	France	CIRAM	France	PRV	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Roberto	Merlo	Male	Italy	Arcanes SARL	France	PRV	SALVATOR MUNDI	Chemistry, humanities, material science, physics, engineering and technology
Elodie	Guilminot	Female	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Cesar	Escobar Claros	Male	Colombia	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Jane	Echinard	Female	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Gilles	Baron	Male	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Stéphane	Lemoine	Male	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	RES	CDHA	Material science

Charlene	Pelé-Meziani	Female	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Loretta	Rosseti	Female	Italy	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Sylvie	Labroche	Female	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Aymeric	Raimon	Male	France	ArcAntique - Grand Patrimoine	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Magali	Brunet	Female	France	Centre d'élaboration de matériaux et d'études structurales - CEMES-CNRS	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Luc	Robbiola	Male	France	Laboratoire TRACES	France	RES	CDHA	Material science
Andrea	Balbo	Male	Italy	University of Ferrara (Department of Engineering)	Italy	UNI	CDHA	Material science
Laura	De Bellis	Female	Italy	University of Ferrara (Department of Engineering)	Italy	UNI	CDHA	Material science
Cristina	Chiavari	Female	Italy	University of Bologna (Department of Cultural Heritage)	Italy	UNI	CDHA	Material science
Carla	Martini	Female	Italy	University of Bologna (Department of Industrial Chemistry "Toso Montanari")	Italy	UNI	CDHA	Material science
Elena	Bernardi	Female	Italy	University of Bologna (Department of Industrial Chemistry "Toso Montanari")	Italy	UNI	CDHA	Material science
Jaromir	Fišer	Male	Czechia	Czech technical university in Prague (Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering)	Czechia	UNI	CDHA	Material science
Michaela	Florescu	Female	France	NOT GIVEN	France	OTH	CDHA	Material science
Jan	Verheyen	Male	Belgium	Catholic University of Leuven (KU Leuven)	Belgium	UNI	Map Philip the Good	Material Science Physics
Geert	Van der Snickt	Male	Belgium	University of Antwerp	Belgium	UNI	Map Philip the Good	Material Science Physics
Anthi	Angeli	Female	Greece	Ephorate of Antiquities of Preveza	Greece	RES	PANDOSIA	Humanities
Dimitra	Drosou	Female	Greece	Ephorate of Antiquities of Preveza	Greece	RES	PANDOSIA	Humanities
Martina	Greisser	Female	Austria	Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna	Austria	OTH	ICARE	Chemistry Humanities Material sciences
Franz	Kirchwegger	Male	Austria	Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna	Austria	OTH	ICARE	Chemistry Humanities Material sciences
Helene	Hanzer	Female	Austria	Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna	Austria	OTH	ICARE	Chemistry Humanities Material sciences
Teresa	Lamers	Female	Austria	Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna	Austria	OTH	ICARE	Chemistry Humanities Material sciences
Katarina	Uhlir	Female	Austria	Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna	Austria	OTH	ICARE	Chemistry Humanities Material sciences
Stefan	Röhrs	Male	Germany	Rathgen-Forschungslabor, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Stiftung	Germany	RES	ICARE	Chemistry Humanities Material sciences

				Preußischer Kulturbesitz				
Maurizio	Aceto	Male	Italy	Università degli Studi del Piemonte Orientale - Dipartimento per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile e la Transizione Ecologica	Italy	UNI	ICARE	Chemistry Humanities Material sciences